

Discussion paper on mechanisms that can ensure that EU policies are coherent with SDGs

MATS Deliverable 4.2

MATS

making agricultural trade sustainable

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Summary

This discussion paper examines the degree of policy coherence between the EU's internal and external policies shaping agricultural trade and the alignment of EU agricultural trade policy and trade agreements in economic, social and environmental terms. Our analysis of all the agreements and political initiatives that make up the “core” trade policy of the EU shows that a small number of trade agreements take into consideration in their provisions the environmental impact of agriculture, including issues such as the impact on soil and water quality, soil erosion, the sustainable use of biological diversity, etc.

Policy coherence is explored at the level of specific EU policies. First, we examine the contribution of organic farming certification and food safety regulations to achieving the relevant sustainable development goals (SDGs). The region- or sector-specific impacts of these policies are examined within the framework of three Case Studies of the project through a detailed questionnaire sent to project partners. We then explore the effects of the possible integration of the Green Deal and Biodiversity Strategy into trade agreements. In addition, we examine the impacts of two CAP elements on trade, especially in developing countries: payments decoupled from production and Coupled Income Support for milk and milk products, sugar, and cotton.

The analysis also includes critical reflections on the dispute settlement mechanisms and efforts to transform the global food system through the UN Food System Summit.

The conclusions of the analysis are divided into different parts: policy coherence and sustainability issues in EU trade-related policies, policy proposals on the EU Organic Farming Certification Scheme, the Harmonised Food Safety regulations for EU imports, and Agricultural Extension and Training; policy coherence and impacts of CAP elements on third countries; general policy-making recommendations; considerations concerning TBTs and SPS; policy recommendations emerging from Policy Briefs of the MATS project's Case Studies, with a short discussion. The Discussion Paper concludes with overall suggestions.

The consecutive CAP reforms completed the shift towards area-based payments, which increased the coherence of the specific EU policy with the EU's global development goals. However, in some cases, the continuation and expansion of coupled payments do not seem to comply with the Policy Coherence for Development principles. Achieving policy coherence between the EU's CAP and the SDGs faces several significant barriers, such as institutional fragmentation, conflicting objectives, regulatory and ideological constraints, lack of comprehensive monitoring

and evaluation, political and economic pressures, and inadequate stakeholder engagement, to name a few. A multifaceted strategy is needed to overcome these obstacles, including stronger institutional coordination, clear regulatory frameworks aligned with sustainability goals, enhanced monitoring mechanisms, and active stakeholder engagement to reconcile diverse policy objectives. Finally, reducing the negative impact of EU external trade on countries in the Global South requires a comprehensive approach that involves policy reforms, enhanced cooperation, and inclusive development strategies.

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Authors: George Vlahos, Pavlos Karanikolas, Spyridon Karytsas (AUA)

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List of Abbreviations

AA	Association Agreement
ACP	African, Caribbean, and Pacific
AMR	Antimicrobial Resistance
AoA	Agreement on Agriculture
AROS	Asia Regional Organic Standard
ARS	African Regional Standard
ASEAN	Association of Southeast Asian Nations
ASOA	ASEAN Standard for Organic Agriculture
BDS	Biodiversity Strategy
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CAPRI	Common Agricultural Policy Regionalised Impact
CETA	Comprehensive and Economic Trade Agreement
CGE	Computable General Equilibrium
COROS	Common Objectives and Requirements of Organic Standards
COVID-19	CoronaVirus Disease of 2019
CS	Case Study
CTEO	Chief Trade Enforcement Officer
DSB	Dispute Settlement Body
DSM	Dispute Settlement Mechanism
EAOPS	East African Organic Products Standard
EBA	Everything but Arms
EEA	European Economic Area
EFTA	European Free Trade Association
EGD	European Green Deal
EPA	Economic Partnership Agreement
ERS	Economic Research Service
EU	European Union
F2F	Farm to Fork
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organisation
FIBL	Research Institute of Organic Agriculture
FSS	Food Systems Summit
FTA	Free Trade Agreement
G20	Group of Twenty
GFI	Gross Farm Income
GHG	Greenhouse Gases
GOMA	Global Organic Market Access
GSP	Generalised Scheme of Preferences
GSP+	Generalised Scheme of Preferences Plus
GTAP-AEZ	Global Trade Analysis Project – AgroEcological Zones
IFOAM	International Federation of Organic Agriculture Movements
ILO	International Labour Organisation
ISDS	Investor-State Dispute Settlement
IT	Information Technology

ITF	International Task Force
ITRIn	Index Global Food System TRIPTOLEMOS Index
JRC	Joint Research Centre
LDCs	Least Developed Countries
LULUCF	Land-Use, Land-Use Change, and Forestry
MAR	Market Access Regulation
MATS	Making Agricultural Trade Sustainable
MEA	Multilateral Environmental Agreement
MRL	Maximum Residue Level
NTM	Non-Tariff Measure
OCTs	Overseas Countries and Territories
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OSA	Open Strategic Autonomy
PC	Policy Coherence
PCD	Policy Coherence for Development
PCSD	Policy Coherence for Sustainable Development
POS	Pacific Organic Standard
PPM	Process and Production Methods
SADC EPA	Southern African Development Community Economic Partnership Agreement
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SEP	Single Entry Point
SIA	Sustainability Impact Assessment
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
SPS	Sanitary and Phytosanitary
SSA	Sub-Saharan Africa
TBT	Technical Barriers to Trade
TRIPS	Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights
TSD	Trade and Sustainable Development
UAA	Utilized Agriculture Area
UN	United Nations
UNCTAD	United Nations Conference on Trade and Development
USDA	United States Department of Agriculture
USSR	Union of Soviet Socialist Republics
VAT	Value Added Tax
WTO	World Trade Organisation

1. AIM, METHODOLOGY AND STRUCTURE OF THE DISCUSSION PAPER

1.1 Aim

The present work is part of the Making Agricultural Trade Sustainable (MATS) project that explores what changes have to be made to agricultural and trade policies to achieve sustainable outcomes. This discussion paper pursues an improved understanding of the coherence of European Union (EU) policy frameworks with respect to their impacts on Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and global agreements on environmental and climate challenges. More specifically, it examines the degree of policy coherence between the EU's internal and external policies shaping agricultural trade and the alignment of EU agricultural trade policy and trade agreements in economic, social, and environmental terms.

The need for logical consistency across all policy development and implementation dimensions has long been emphasised. Policy coherence for sustainable development (PCSD) is an approach and policy tool for integrating the various dimensions of sustainable development at all policy-making stages. Also, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) emphasise the need for coordinated action through mutually beneficial policies. Undoubtedly, this is a formidable task. It requires a holistic approach to address development difficulties, adopting mutually reinforcing policies across all key sectors and limiting adverse effects that policies in one area might have on others. It necessitates suitable institutional frameworks that promote coordination and integration, quantitative and analytical abilities to find and evaluate synergies and trade-offs between various policy alternatives, and accurate data for evidence-based policies.

Thus, within the framework of the 2030 Agenda, PCSD aims to (i) Promote synergies and optimise benefits among economic, social, and environmental policy domains; (ii) Identify trade-offs and harmonise national policy goals with globally acknowledged sustainable development objectives; and (iii) Address the spillovers of domestic policies.

The OECD has been at the forefront of elaborating on the concept of PCSD and developing a set of relevant indicators that provide a common language and metrics for tracking progress towards PCSD. The key elements for tracking progress on PCSD are depicted in Figure 1.1.

In addition, a distinction is made between vertical and horizontal coherence. Vertical coherence focuses on integrating specific issues and activities into specific sectors and the various policy levels and scales within those sectors. Horizontal coherence, on the other hand, focuses on interactions between different sectors and institutions that share the same level of accountability (e.g., regional, national or local) (Figure 1.2).

Figure 1.1 The building blocks of Policy Coherence

Source: OECD, 2016

Figure 1.2 Vertical and Horizontal Coherence

Source: Curran et al., 2018

1.2 Methodology

In attaining Task 4.2, we first examine the EU's trade relationships by country/region to identify the provisions in the relevant trade agreements concerning sustainability within agricultural trade - or sector in general. This

investigation concerns all types of Agreements (e.g., Free Trade Agreements, Association Agreements, Customs unions, Economic Partnership Agreements) and their status, i.e., Agreements in place, Agreements being adopted or ratified, and Agreements being negotiated. A special reference is made to the dispute settlement mechanisms and their ability to change the power imbalances in trade relationships.

We then refine the concept of PCSD by selecting specific EU policies for which we seek to identify (i) their synergies and trade-offs with SDGs and (ii) their spillovers. The selection of policies/initiatives has been made based on the following criteria: impacts on food security; regional differentiation of impacts on food security, income, prices, and trade volume; impacts on small farms /firms; significance; availability of empirical analysis; and covered by MATS case studies.

Thus, two existing and one prospective EU policies/initiatives have been selected.

Existing policies: Organic farming certification and Food Safety. Prospective policies: Green Deal/Biodiversity (Farm to Fork).

Subsequently, three of the 15 MATS case studies (CS) have been selected to receive feedback on the region or sector-specific impacts of the policies examined:

- CS1, "Reducing poverty among smallholder farmers through enhanced trade regimes and value chains for coffee in Uganda and Tanzania," was selected as the first CS relevant to two policies: Organic Certification and Food Safety Regulations.
- CS4 on "Enhancing Access to Export Markets by Sub-Saharan African Countries through Sustainable Investments to Ensure Quality and Quality of Agri-food Commodities: The Cases of Tanzania, Uganda, Ethiopia, and Ghana" was the second CS study relevant to two policies: Organic Certification and Food Safety Regulations.
- CS6, "Analysis of cocoa and chocolate purchasing practices that could undermine living incomes for cocoa farmers", was a sectoral one that analysed the whole cocoa market.

A questionnaire was prepared and sent to project partners of the three CSs to get feedback on the role each specific policy is playing in the CS and the sectors concerned. The first task of this exercise was to evaluate the specific policies within the framework of the specific CSs concerning their contribution to achieving the relevant Goals and Targets of the Sustainable Development Agenda 2030. The task leaders prepared a list of goals and targets and sent them to the CS-related partners for this purpose. Partners were asked to evaluate the synergies and trade-offs of each policy with SDGs using a 7-point scale (see Fig. 3). More specifically, positive interactions are assigned scores of +1 ('enabling'), +2 ('reinforcing') or +3 ('indivisible'), while interactions

characterised by trade-offs are scored with -1 ('constraining'), -2 ('counteracting'), or -3 ('cancelling'); neutral interactions are assigned 0.

Figure 1.3 Evaluation of synergies and trade-offs

Further, more policy-specific questions were posed to elicit the relevant CS information necessary to analyse the results. Finally, policy proposals were provided by CS partners.

As far as the prospective policies (policies that have recently been enacted or are to be enacted soon), we examine the effects of possible integration of the Green Deal and Biodiversity Strategy in currently under negotiation or future trade Agreements. The discussion focuses on the restrictions imposed that are directly linked to agricultural production and, at the same time, offer the possibility to draw quantifiable estimations of the impacts.

Moreover, it is well known that the EU's external trade often negatively affects the Global South. Thus, apart from the external impacts of the policies mentioned above, we examine EU internal policies in the light of the "Policy Coherence for Development" principles. More concretely, we explore the impacts of two different elements of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) on trade, especially in developing countries, including Least Developed Countries (LDCs): (a) payments decoupled from production, such as the single farm payment or as it is currently called Basic Income Support for Sustainability, where farmers are paid an annual support per eligible hectare and (b) Coupled Income Support (previously called Voluntary Coupled Support), where EU member-states (MS) are allowed to support specific sectors or productions (including the crop-specific payment for cotton) to improve competitiveness, sustainability, and/or quality. Three products/sectors receiving coupled support due to their important repercussions for developing countries are specifically mentioned: milk and milk products, sugar, and cotton.

The choice was to focus on these CAP tools since the other two, namely (c) Market-related measures again for specific sectors and finally (d) rural development measures, exert an influence similar to the one by decoupled payments in the sense that they act as an incentive for production since they play a role in the maintenance of marginally viable sectors and products and encourage investment (Blanco, 2018).

1.3 Structure of the Discussion Paper

After the introductory section, the second chapter of this discussion paper presents the new EU trade policy and the provisions of EU trade Agreements on sustainability aspects and the agricultural trade/sector. Section 2.2 examines existing trade-related policies already being implemented, while in section 2.3, elements of sustainability in current EU trade policy are explored. This exploration concerns all the agreements and political initiatives that make up the 'core' trade policy of the EU, i.e., 44 "Agreements in place" involving 77 countries/regions and 5 "Agreements being adopted or ratified" involving 25 countries/ regions. A central part of our study was identifying provisions in the trade agreements under consideration, focusing specifically on the agricultural trade/sector concerning sustainability aspects. Section 2.4 refers to dispute settlement mechanisms.

The third chapter reviews existing studies and policy evaluations on the quest for policy coherence in EU agricultural and trade policies. It also includes a section concerning efforts to transform the food system and achieve the SDGs, specifically the UN food system summit, designed to foster collaboration, innovation, and collective action to transform the food system and achieve the SDGs.

The fourth chapter includes the examination of the policy issues that have been identified within the diversity of policies enacted or initiated by the EU: (i) organic farming certification, (ii) food safety regulations, and (iii) Green Deal and Biodiversity Strategy (BDS) targets. Feedback on the region- or sector-specific impacts of the policies examined is then presented from three of the MATS case studies. The Green Deal and BDS targets have been selected as prospective EU policies, i.e., recently enacted policies. Thus, the following subsection includes the potential effects of integrating the Green Deal and Biodiversity 2030 rules into trade agreements. This is followed by referencing the expected effects of the F2F (Farm to Fork) Strategy on production, consumption, and trade. In light of the Policy Coherence for Development principles, the section on EU internal policies concludes the chapter (payments decoupled from production and Coupled Income Support for milk and milk products, sugar, and cotton).

The conclusions and recommendations are presented in the fifth chapter. After the conclusions on policy coherence and sustainability issues in EU trade-related policies, the policy proposals follow the EU Organic Farming Certification Scheme, the Harmonised Food Safety regulations for EU imports, and Agricultural Extension and Training. The following sections concern the policy coherence and impacts of CAP elements on third countries; general policy-

making recommendations; considerations concerning Technical Barriers to Trade (TBTs) and Sanitary and Phytosanitary (SPS) Measures; policy recommendations emerging from Policy Briefs of the MATS project's Case Studies. A short discussion follows on a few additional issues noted in the literature concerning the observations and recommendations provided by MATS Case Studies partners. The chapter concludes with overall suggestions.

2. EU TRADE AGREEMENTS: PROVISIONS ON SUSTAINABILITY ASPECTS AND THE AGRICULTURAL TRADE/SECTOR

2.1 The new EU Trade Policy

The EU's current view on its trade policy is set out in a comprehensive report entitled 'Trade Policy Review - An Open, Sustainable and Assertive Trade Policy' (**European Commission, 2021**). According to this report, the EU needs a new trade strategy to address the challenges of economic recovery, climate change and environmental degradation, growing international tensions, greater recourse to unilateralism, and its consequences for multilateral institutions. The new strategy will, therefore, further integrate EU trade policy within the economic priorities as reflected in the Green Deal and the European Digital strategy, specify trade policy's role in the post-COVID economic recovery, and support the pursuit of the EU's geopolitical ambitions. As such, it will show how trade policy endorses the EU's Open Strategic Autonomy (OSA). The new strategy aims to establish a new consensus for trade policy based on openness, sustainability, and assertiveness. It reinforces the EU's position as a global champion of open, rules-based trade that is fair and sustainable.

Also, the EU's trade policy needs to focus on three core objectives: supporting the recovery and fundamental transformation of the EU economy in line with its green and digital objectives; shaping global rules for a more sustainable and fairer globalization; increasing the EU's capacity to pursue its interests and enforce its rights, including autonomous actions where needed. To deliver these three objectives, the Commission will focus on (i) Reforming the WTO (World Trade Organization), (ii) Supporting the green transition and promoting responsible and sustainable value chains, (iii) Promoting the digital transition and trade in services, (iv) Strengthening the EU's regulatory impact (v) Deepening EU's partnerships with neighbouring, enlargement countries and Africa (vi) Reinforcing the EU's focus on implementing and enforcing trade agreements and ensuring a level playing field for EU businesses. For each of these areas, the strategy sets out a number of headline actions to be accomplished during the current Commission's mandate.

Moreover, the OSA reflects the EU's desire to chart its course on the global stage, shaping the world through leadership and engagement while preserving its interests and values. OSA foresees making the best possible use of the opportunities of the EU's openness and global engagement while assertively defending the EU's interests, both internally and externally. In essence, the EU will continue working with partners to advance this positive agenda but will work autonomously when necessary.

Furthermore, the EU will remain open to trade and investment. The EU has a strong network of trade agreements (44 "Agreements in place", involving 77 countries/ regions, apart from the EU part of the agreement and 5 "Agreements being adopted or ratified", involving 25 countries/ regions, apart from the EU

part of the agreement), and a substantial trade surplus. Across the EU, 35 million jobs depend on trade. Many are high-quality jobs, while competitive gains from global trade have increased wages by 12-fold. There is the potential to build on this solid foundation, but to do so, the EU has to look beyond the borders, given that 85% of global growth will occur outside Europe in the next decade. The best way to ensure the EU's prosperity is to keep trading with its international partners rather than turning inward. Indeed, more than ever, there is a need to open trade to support recovery from the COVID-19 pandemic. The EU is and will remain a champion of openness and global cooperation, a global economic power, and a leader in sustainable growth. Nevertheless, being open does not mean being defenceless. The EU will defend itself from unfair trade practices. The EU is built on and needs openness to strengthen resilience and help keep its industries competitive, to make the Single Market more attractive, and to tackle climate change and other environmental challenges. Openness and engagement are strategic choices that lead to more prosperity, competitiveness, and dynamism.

The EU has been and continues to be steadfast in its support for multilateralism and a rules-based international order. The EU wants to update the global rulebook so that its rules consider the profound economic developments in recent decades. Such reform is needed to ensure the stability and predictability necessary for trade to thrive. The EU's new strategy sets out an agenda to reform the WTO by adopting a first set of WTO reforms focusing on sustainable development and working towards mainstreaming sustainability in the work of the Organization, reinforcing WTO rules against negative spill-overs of state intervention in member economies.

In addition, the EU intends to intensify its engagement with Africa and its neighbouring countries, including enlargement countries, and to consolidate its partnerships with key growth regions, notably Latin America and Asia-Pacific. Finally, the transatlantic relationship is the world's most significant and economically important partnership. It is deeply rooted in shared interests and values. It is essential to work with the US administration to reform the WTO by reinforcing its capacity to tackle competitive distortions and contribute to sustainable development. It also offers new prospects to cooperate closely on both economies' green and digital transformation.

The EU is crucial in promoting a transition to sustainable and resilient food systems, with its ambitious Green Deal and global role in agri-food markets. While examining the application of EU health and environmental standards to imported agricultural and agri-food products, the **European Commission (2022a)** holds that the COVID-19 crisis and Russia's invasion of Ukraine have exposed vulnerabilities in agricultural and food systems, necessitating a shift towards a sustainable and resilient EU food system. The EU's ambitious health, environmental, and sustainability standards contribute to achieving legitimate global concerns, aligning with the 'One Health' approach. To enhance and promote health and environmental standards, the EU will continue its efforts at a multilateral level, intensifying its efforts and fostering better coordination and synergies.

Trade agreements and bilateral cooperation offer opportunities to achieve sustainability standards with partner countries. The EU has already made progress in this area with its ambitious trade agenda, including a TSD chapter and provisions on cooperation on animal welfare and AMR (Antimicrobial Resistance), while a Sustainable Food Systems chapter is proposed in future agreements.

Considering trade impacts on third countries, the EU will ensure the coherence of its sustainability agenda with its enlargement, neighbourhood, and development policies. Flanking measures, including funding, technical cooperation, and capacity building, may assist trading partners in engaging in more sustainable practices, especially for vulnerable countries and neighbouring partners undertaking ambitious commitments in those fields.

The EU can take measures autonomously to address global environmental concerns or animal welfare issues when necessary. However, applying Process and Production Method (PPM) regulations to imported products must be done in full respect of WTO rules and international commitments. Measures considered illegitimate or protectionist and inconsistent with the EU's international obligations and rights may expose the EU to a risk of retaliation.

Regulatory proposals need to undergo a case-by-case assessment of their WTO compatibility. Each case must be carefully analysed on its merits, considering control mechanisms' technical and economic feasibility. The feasibility and proportionality of adequate means to control and enforce these measures must be assessed in relation to the costs and benefits of doing so.

The coherence of the CAP with the Green Deal and trade policy is crucial for farmers' economic growth, competitiveness, and environmental performance. However, as the **European Commission (2022b)** stresses, concerns have arisen that the F2F Strategy may lead to the off-shoring of food and agricultural production overseas, potentially undermining policy objectives. To ensure the F2F Strategy benefits farmers and European society, it is essential to ensure coherence between agricultural, environmental, and trade policies. The AgriFish Council has identified three levels of action: autonomous measures, multilateral actions, and bilateral actions. Autonomous measures can be justified for ethical reasons or to protect global sustainability concerns, but they must comply with WTO rules. Multilateral actions should be promoted in relevant fora, including the FAO (Food and Agriculture Organisation) /Codex, WTO, and G20, while considering the varying levels of development among partners, particularly in the least-developed countries and middle-income countries. Bilateral actions should be taken to foster the EU's sustainability agenda and enhance cooperation in sustainable food systems. The European Commission is working on a report to examine how to achieve coherence between agricultural, environmental, and trade policies.

The Hilton beef quota is a potential example of a sustainable agenda; however, further discussion is needed to ensure its effectiveness with trade partners. The European Commission has made commitments in the Trade Policy Review and F2F Strategy and is working on a report to achieve coherence between

agricultural, environmental, and trade policies. The report will assess the rationale and legal feasibility of these approaches.

2.2 Existing trade-related policies, already being implemented

Several agreements and political initiatives make up the 'core' trade policy of the EU. Currently, the EU has 44 "Agreements in place", involving 77 countries/regions and 5 "Agreements being adopted or ratified", involving 25 countries/regions.

There are various types of these agreements:

- **Free trade agreements (FTAs)** enable reciprocal market opening with developed countries and emerging economies by granting preferential access to markets.
- **Economic partnership agreements (EPAs)** are a particular type of FTAs. EPAs are trade and development arrangements between the EU and the African, Caribbean, and Pacific (ACP) countries - designed to facilitate the ACPs' integration into the world economy through gradual trade liberalisation and improved trade-related cooperation.
- **Association agreements (AAs)** strengthen broader political agreements. For example, the deals with Ukraine and Georgia aim to deepen political ties and strengthen economic links with the two countries.
- **Customs Union deals** with Turkey, Andorra, and San Marino. The Customs Unions provide free movement of goods between the two parts of the customs union, alignment on external tariffs, harmonised commercial policy measures, common standards, mutual assistance in customs matters, and cooperation in other fields.
- **The Comprehensive and Economic Trade Agreement (CETA)** is a trade deal between the EU and Canada. It aims to boost trade and help generate growth and jobs. CETA lowers customs tariffs and other barriers to trade between the EU and Canada.

In addition, besides EPAs, the EU has special trade arrangements in place in support of **developing countries**:

- **Generalised Scheme of Preferences (GSP):** The EU offers its current GSP to low and lower-middle-income countries under several multilateral and bilateral agreements and by unilateral waivers. The scheme partially or fully removes EU customs duties for many products coming into the EU market.
- **Generalised Scheme of Preferences Plus (GSP+):** This is a special incentive arrangement for sustainable development and good governance. It cuts EU import customs tariffs to 0% for vulnerable low and lower-middle-income countries that implement 27 international conventions related to human rights, labour rights, protection of the environment, and good governance.

- **Everything but Arms (EBA):** a special arrangement for least developed countries, which grants full duty-free and quota-free access to the EU Single Market for all products except arms and armament.

It has to be noted that some clarifications about tariff quotas are provided in Appendix I.

Other specific trade arrangements include:

- **Market Access Regulation (MAR):** it provides duty-free quota-free access to the EU market for products originating in those ACP countries that do not benefit from an EBA regime and have concluded EPAs pending ratification.
- **European Economic Area (EEA):** The EEA brings the 27 EU member states and three European Free Trade Association (EFTA) nations - Iceland, Liechtenstein, and Norway - together in the EU Single Market, guaranteeing the freedom of movement for goods, services, people and capital, as well as unified related policies (competition, transport, energy, economic and monetary cooperation).
- **Overseas Countries and Territories (OCTs):** The OCTs are not part of the European Community territory but are constitutionally linked to three Member States (Denmark, France, and the Netherlands). The European Community grants unilateral trade preferences to all products originating in the OCTs, aiming to promote their economic and social development and establish close economic relations between them and the Community.

International agricultural trade is also strongly affected by the **WTO Agreement on Agriculture (AoA)**, which came into force on 1 January 1995, making a decisive move towards the objective of increased market orientation in agricultural trade. The AoA includes four main parts: the AoA itself; the concessions and commitments Members undertake on market access, domestic support, and export subsidies; the Agreement on SPS Measures; and the Ministerial Decision concerning Least-Developed and Net Food-Importing Developing countries.

On the basis of the AoA, WTO Member States undertook the implementation of **an agricultural policy reform agenda** that lays down specific binding commitments in three major areas: market access, domestic support, and export subsidies. In addition, some provisions of the Agreement on the Application of **SPS Measures** also involve agricultural production and trade; this agreement sets out the basic rules on food safety and animal and plant health standards that governments must follow. Also, the AoA provisions are supplemented by the Agreement on TBTs and technical assistance mechanisms. SPS and TBT seek to identify how to meet the need to apply standards while avoiding disguised protectionism. Furthermore, **the Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS)** involves agricultural trade and production through the protection of geographical designations, a sector of major importance for European agriculture.

Finally, the AoA includes a **Dispute Settlement Body (DSB)** with a stringent dispute procedure, ensuring that signatory states comply with the new multilateral rules.

The Agreement also considers **non-trade concerns**, including food security and the need to protect the environment. It provides special and differential treatment for developing countries, including improving the opportunities and terms of access for agricultural products of particular export interest to these Members. It has to be noted that these agreements contain a certain degree of **flexibility** regarding their implementation by developing countries, WTO members (special and differential treatment), Least Developed Countries (LDCs), and net food-importing developing countries (special provisions).

Within the debate on EU food safety and environmental standards, one of the concerns of the EU, since 2021-2022, is the willingness to introduce reciprocity in agri-food trade agreements, known as '**mirror clauses**'. Mirror clauses, which require all EU trading partners to adhere to the same or similar environmental and sustainability standards as the EU, are an example of a unilateral measure.

As mirror clauses are intended to ensure that imported goods are produced following the same sanitary, phytosanitary, welfare, and environmental standards as those imposed on domestic goods within the EU, their introduction has clear implications for **Process and Production Methods (PPMs)**. When a nation's trade policy is driven by a desire to ensure that imports have been produced in a way that complies with a national or international production or process norm, production and processing methods are used. These norms frequently have an environmental component.

2.3 Aspects of sustainability in current trade policy

EU's trade relationships were examined by country/region to identify the provisions in the relevant trade agreements concerning sustainability within agricultural trade -or sector in general. To do so, the list of agreements provided by the European Commission was taken into account; the complete list of agreements is available at https://policy.trade.ec.europa.eu/eu-trade-relationships-country-and-region/negotiations-and-agreements_en (EU trade relationships by country/region -> Negotiations and agreements). In specific, 44 "Agreements in place" (involving 77 countries/ regions, apart from the EU part of the agreement) and 5 "Agreements being adopted or ratified" (involving 25 countries/ regions, apart from the EU part of the agreement) were taken into consideration. It should be noted that the "Agreements being negotiated" were not considered in this study.

As a first indication, it could be noted that the majority of the trade agreements include some general provisions (not agricultural-focused) concerning the economic cooperation policies between the two parts (i.e., the EU and the corresponding country/region) on sustainable development, taking into consideration the economic, environmental, and social dimensions of

sustainability (in specific, among all cases examined, less than 10% of the agreements do not include any sustainability-focused provisions; most of these agreements are formed and applied prior to 2000). The specific text may differ among the Agreements (in many cases, depending on the timeframe of the Agreement, i.e., when the Agreement was shaped); however, a typical example of such a provision, coming from the Agreement with Albania, is the following (Article 86 - Stabilisation and association agreement between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Albania, of the other part; In force since 2009): "*Policies and other measures shall be designed to bring about sustainable economic and social development of Albania. These policies should ensure that environmental considerations are also fully incorporated from the outset and that they are linked to the requirements of harmonious social development*". Another example that could be quoted is that from the agreement with the SADC EPA States (Article 6 - Economic Partnership Agreement between the European Union and its Member States, of the one part, and the SADC EPA States, of the other part; Provisionally applied since 2016-2019, depending on the SADC State): "*The Parties reaffirm their commitments to promote the development of international trade in such a way as to contribute to the objective of sustainable development, in its three pillars (economic development, social development, and environmental protection) for the welfare of present and future generations, and will strive to ensure that this objective is integrated and reflected at every level of their trade relationship*". In brief, when referring to (cooperation for) TSD provisions in the examined trade agreements, themes such as the following are taken into consideration; it should be noted that the themes differ significantly among the examined agreements:

- In general, human, cultural, economic, social, health, and environmental best interests of the respective populations and future generations;
- **Environmental/ ecological aspects:** climate change; low carbon technologies; energy efficiency; (sustainable use of) biological diversity; preserved natural resources; management of forests; forestry certification schemes and traceability of different forestry products; sustainable fishing practices; combating illegal trade with environmental relevance;
- **Labour aspects:** International Labour Organisation (ILO) Decent Work Agenda; Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work (freedom of association and collective bargaining, forced labour, child labour, no employment discrimination); workers' rights; minimum living wage health and safety at work; labour market adjustment; labour standards; interlinkages between trade and productive employment; labour statistics; human resources development; and lifelong learning;
- **Social/ health aspects:** social protection; social inclusion; freedom; human dignity; social justice; security and non-discrimination; gender equality; social dialogue; public health; reduction and eradication of poverty;

- **Market/ trade aspects:** corporate social responsibility and accountability; private and public certification; sustainability assurance schemes/ labelling and marketing initiatives (e.g., fair and ethical trade, eco-labelling, green public procurement); development of rural and urban micro, SMEs; customs cooperation;
- **Sustainable consumption and production:** circular economy; economic models increasing resource efficiency; reduction of waste generation; sustainability of food systems.

Following the general provisions on sustainable development, the trade agreements include provisions specifying the cooperation policies relevant to sustainability's economic, environmental, and social aspects. With our focus on the agricultural sector, it is worth noting that a small number of trade agreements (agreements involving 11 out of the 102 examined countries) specifically take into consideration in their provisions the environmental impact of agriculture, including issues such as a) the impact on soil and water quality, b) soil erosion and pollution by agricultural chemicals, c) the management of impacts through the use of antibiotics and decontaminants, d) conservation and sustainable use of biological diversity, and e) genetically modified organisms. As examples of such provisions, the agreements with North Macedonia (Article 103 - Stabilisation and association agreement between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia, of the other part; In force since 2004), mentioning that "*Cooperation could centre on the following priorities: [...] the environmental impact of agriculture; soil erosion and pollution by agricultural chemicals, ...*", and with Algeria (Article 52 - Euro-Mediterranean association agreement between the European Community and its Members States, of the one part, and the People's Democratic Republic of Algeria, of the other part; In force since 2005), mentioning that "*Cooperation shall in particular focus on: [...] the impact of agriculture on soil and water quality...*" could be quoted.

Moreover, it is worth highlighting that in several cases (agreements involving 31 out of the 102 countries taken into consideration), provisions focusing on or taking into consideration the aspect of climate/ climate change are also present in the trade agreements, without -however- making a specific mention to the agricultural trade or sector. For example, the Trade Agreement with Kosovo (Stabilisation and association agreement between the European Union and the European Atomic Energy Community, of the one part, and Kosovo, of the other part; In force since 2016) includes the phrase "...environmental and climate considerations...", in the general provision on cooperation policies (Article 93), while also including a specific provision taking into consideration climate change (Article 116): "*The Parties shall cooperate with the aim to assist Kosovo to develop its climate policy and mainstream climate consideration in energy, transport, industry, agriculture, education and other relevant policies. [...] The Parties shall cooperate with the aim, should objective circumstances so permit, to assist Kosovo's involvement in global and regional efforts to mitigate and adapt to climate change.*". Depending on the agreement, different climate change-related themes are included in the provisions, including:

- Mitigation of climate change;
- Adaptation to climate change;
- Market and non-market approaches to addressing climate change;
- Carbon trading/ global carbon markets;
- Strengthening of carbon market mechanisms;
- Mainstreaming of climate considerations into sector policies;
- Exchange of climate expertise and support for other sectors;
- Awareness raising, education, and training;
- Low-carbon and adaptation technologies, sustainable renewable energy, and energy efficiency;
- Reduction of emissions from deforestation and forest degradation.

Finally, a central part of our study was to identify provisions in the trade agreements under consideration, focusing specifically on the agricultural trade/sector concerning sustainability aspects. Among the 49 agreements examined, 34 included some provision/s focusing on the sustainability aspects of the agricultural trade/sector. A special mention could be made to the Economic Partnership Agreement between the East African Community Partner States (i.e., Burundi, Kenya, Rwanda, Tanzania, and Uganda) and the EU, with its agricultural-related chapter including 18 articles, most of them being relevant to sustainable-related themes. The full texts of the identified provisions are available in Appendix II. In a nutshell, when referring to agricultural trade/sector-related provisions in terms of sustainability aspects, themes such as the following are reflected; as indicated above, the themes differ significantly among the examined agreements:

- **Production/ technical aspects:** improved production, productivity (e.g., seed program, integrated pest management, biotechnologies, disease handling) and diversification; modernisation of infrastructures and equipment (e.g., irrigation facilities, water management); development of packaging, storage, and marketing techniques; capacity-building, infrastructure and technology transfer; exchange of best practices; technical assistance, education, training, and information events; support for research programs; preservation of agricultural traditional knowledge;
- **Financial/ Market aspects:** modernisation, diversification, and restructuring of the agriculture, agro-industrial, and service sectors; development of agri-business; cooperation in the agriculture, forestry, and rural development sectors; increased competitiveness; promotion of agricultural service cooperatives; attention to small scale operations; agricultural financing services (e.g., insurance schemes and instruments for access to finance); improved distribution channels and marketing chains; certification instruments (e.g., electronic certification);

- **Regulatory/ policy aspects:** agricultural and rural development policies; regional CAP; policies aiming to diversify production; policies and legislation on agricultural biotechnology products; food production and marketing quality standards (e.g., standards on agricultural practices, organic and non-genetically modified foods, and geographical indications); sanitary, phytosanitary and veterinary standards; water management, veterinary, plant health, and quality regulations;
- **Environmental/ Ecological aspects:** environmentally sound practices; sustainable management of natural resources; agricultural water resources; environmental health, animal and plant health; protection of animal welfare; forestry sector (i.e., reforestation, forest fire prevention, forest pasture and combating desertification);
- **Social/ health aspects:** food security; poverty eradication; cooperation in health; livelihoods of rural and fishing communities; rural employment; income of farm households; economic well-being for rural communities; sustainable rural development; secured livelihood.

2.4 Dispute Settlement Mechanisms

2.4.1 WTO and EU

Dispute Settlement Mechanisms (DSMs) are formal processes designed to resolve trade disputes between countries fairly, transparently, and rules-based. They provide a platform for countries to raise concerns, negotiate, and settle disputes without resorting to retaliatory measures or trade wars.

According to the **European Commission's Directorate-General for Trade [n.a.(a)]**, the EU employs a range of mechanisms to uphold its commitments in international trade agreements, benefiting businesses, workers, and citizens alike. One of these tools is dispute settlement, a "neutral and efficient" means of resolving conflicts between countries or between investors and governments regarding policies or practices. By doing so:

- It prevents unilateral actions and helps to de-escalate diplomatic tensions, ultimately contributing to peaceful international relations.
- It clarifies countries' obligations under international law and fosters a common understanding through case law.

Dispute settlements operate under the framework of the WTO or through EU bilateral trade agreements:

- WTO dispute settlement: The WTO offers a dedicated process for its member countries to resolve disputes that arise when one country believes another is not complying with the terms of a WTO trade agreement or commitment. When a dispute arises, the WTO's DSM springs into action, allowing countries to resolve their differences. The WTO's DSM is one of the most active and effective worldwide, with a remarkable track record of resolving disputes. Since 1995, over 624

disputes have been brought to the WTO, and more than 350 rulings have been issued [**European Commission, n.a.(b); World Trade Organization, n.a.**].

- Bilateral dispute settlement: The EU incorporates a dispute settlement mechanism into all its trade agreements, enabling the EU and its trading partners to resolve disputes that may arise efficiently. Modelled after the WTO dispute settlement system, this mechanism is designed to facilitate swift and effective dispute resolution. Specifically, it is tailored to address issues related to the rules and regulations outlined in the EU's bilateral trade agreements, ensuring that disagreements are resolved promptly and fairly [**European Commission, n.a.(c)**].
- Investment dispute settlement: Following the Lisbon Treaty's implementation in 2009, the EU's common commercial policy now encompasses foreign direct investment. Since then, the EU has been negotiating with third countries to establish investment protection and liberalization rules. These agreements include a mechanism that enables investors to take disputes against governments to independent tribunals if they believe the government has breached the agreement. The EU is also a signatory to the Energy Charter Treaty, which provides for investment dispute settlement. Furthermore, the European Commission has been working since 2015 to establish a Multilateral Investment Court, which aims to provide a more efficient and transparent dispute resolution system. Globally, over 3,000 bilateral investment treaties are in force, with more than 1,400 of these agreements concluded by EU Member States. The majority of these treaties include a dispute settlement mechanism for investors. EU investors are the most frequent users of these mechanisms worldwide [**European Commission, n.a.(d)**].

2.4.2 Can Dispute Settlement Mechanisms change the power imbalances in trade relationships?

Power imbalances in trade relationships are a long-standing issue that has hindered countries' ability, particularly developing ones, to benefit fully from international trade. These imbalances often stem from differences in economic size, market access, and institutional capacity between trading partners. The lack of a level playing field can lead to unequal trade agreements, where one party wields significant influence over the other. This, in turn, can result in unfavourable terms of trade, limited market access, and a lack of protection for domestic industries.

DSMs have been touted as a potential solution to address these power imbalances; they have enabled developing countries to challenge unfair trade practices and level the playing field with their developed counterparts by providing a formal process for resolving trade disputes. For instance, in 2002, Brazil successfully challenged the United States' cotton subsidies at the WTO, resulting in a landmark ruling that forced the US to modify its agricultural subsidies.

Although DSMs have played a significant role in changing the power balance in trade relationships, the question remains: *Can DSMs truly change the power imbalances in trade relationships?* The answer is not straightforward. On the one hand, DSMs can provide a safety net for weaker trading partners, allowing them to challenge unfair trade practices and seek redress without fear of retaliation. This can help to level the playing field, enabling smaller countries to negotiate more favourable trade agreements and protect their domestic industries.

On the other hand, the effectiveness of DSMs in addressing power imbalances is contingent upon several factors. Firstly, the DSM must be designed and implemented to ensure equal access and opportunities for all parties involved. This means that the process should be transparent, with clear rules and procedures, and that all parties have the necessary resources and capacity to participate effectively.

Secondly, the DSM must be able to address the underlying power imbalances that exist in trade relationships. This may involve providing additional support and capacity-building measures for weaker trading partners, such as technical assistance, training, and financial support. Without such measures, the DSM may simply perpetuate the existing power dynamic, with stronger countries continuing to dominate the negotiation process.

Consequently, while DSMs have the potential to mitigate power imbalances in trade relationships, their effectiveness depends on their design, implementation, and the broader context in which they operate. To truly effect change, DSMs must be part of a broader strategy that addresses the structural inequalities in international trade. This requires a commitment to reforming the global trading system, promoting greater cooperation and collaboration between countries, and fostering a more equitable distribution of benefits from international trade.

Furthermore, one of the best-known forms of arbitration, the Investor-State Dispute Settlement (ISDS), has been severely criticized; ISDS is a form of arbitration in which an investor can sue a government for a policy measure before a special tribunal outside national courts. ISDS is unidirectional. Cases can only be filed by investors alone. It is not feasible to do the reverse. Nations cannot use such a court, nor can human rights advocates, labour union executives, or environmentalists. Consequently, a system that safeguards human rights, the ecology, and the climate should replace the one that shields investors (**Trade Differently, 2021**).

Finally, a significant crisis recently occurred in the WTO's dispute settlement process. Because the US prevented appointments to the Appellate Body, its appeals process is non-operational. Because of this, most panel reports have been appealed "into the void," leaving the dispute unresolved (**IISD, 2022**).

3. THE QUEST FOR POLICY COHERENCE IN EU AGRICULTURAL AND TRADE POLICIES – EFFORTS TO TRANSFORM THE FOOD SYSTEM AND ACHIEVE THE SDGS

3.1 A review of existing studies and policy evaluations

The policy coherence between the EU's Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and trade policy has been a subject of extensive analysis and debate.

Schmitz and Eimer (2020) explore the rise of policy coherence in EU external policy, highlighting how traditionally siloed areas like trade and agriculture are increasingly integrated, aiming for a more unified external policy approach. **Bossuyt et al. (2020)** focus on the trade-foreign policy nexus, arguing that synergetic coherence is hampered by institutional and ideological constraints within the EU, such as the pro-liberalization bias and export-oriented interests. **McMahon (2013)** assesses the EU's negotiating position in the Doha Round, noting that while there are opportunities for promoting Policy Coherence for Development (PCD) through CAP reform, these are not fully realized, especially in sectors like cotton. **Mikuš et al. (2019)** review the coherence of CAP with regional policies, emphasizing conflicts between cohesion and competitiveness objectives that impact balanced territorial development. **Stocchetti (2013)** comprehensively analyses the EU's normative power and PCD in global governance, using the European Consensus on Development and trade policy as key examples.

Carbone and Keijzer (2016) argue that EU member states have acknowledged PCD's importance but have not followed their pledges with more cohesive (national and supranational) policies. They conclude that effective PCD promotion is primarily a political endeavour rather than merely relying on strong arguments and adequate technical backing.

According to **Coderoni (2023)**, Policy Coherence (PC) ought to be pursued both *within policy* and *between policies*. The CAP was examined as the main EU agricultural policy to analyse the PC. The primary obstacles to incorporating environmental goals into the CAP are associated with implementing the Producer Pays Principle, which also necessitates establishing a suitable baseline, handling response heterogeneity, addressing spatial issues, and selecting the appropriate policy instrument. These arguments all point to the need for more targeted and customized policies, which will undoubtedly profit from digitalization's new tools. Rather than reaching a consensus between PC, an analytical task to find trade-offs and synergies among policy objectives should be developed after the policy framework has been simplified. When synergies occur, policymakers should understand that there are rarely "silver bullets" and that different policy instruments are usually needed to achieve multiple objectives. These instruments should be properly calibrated using a primarily "technical" approach. Changing the chosen policy instrument is frequently the solution when trade-offs

between conflicting objectives occur. If trade-offs continue, decisions about values should be made, explicitly stating both domestic and transboundary trade-offs to facilitate transparent and cooperative decision-making.

Scown et al. (2020) assess how well the CAP accomplishes its many social and environmental objectives and examine how well CAP indicators align with different policy stages and CAP Pillars. They found that the current CAP monitoring system's indicators are skewed toward a small number of goals, making it impossible to balance many potentially conflicting goals. More concretely, three goals are the focus of the current CAP indicators: life on land (SDG 15), decent work (SDG 8), and zero hunger (SDG 2). Significant SDGs such as health (SDG 3), gender equality (SDG 5), oceans (SDG 14), and institutions (SDG 16) are entirely absent from the agricultural indicators, which runs counter to recent reports claiming that agriculture contributes to all SDGs worldwide. They discovered that Pillar II of the CAP supports rural development, and the CAP Target, Result, and Impact indicator best addresses the SDGs.

Adelle and Jordan (2014) have examined coherence issues in the EU's sugar policy. They contend that this policy perpetuated the conflicts that previously thwarted agricultural reform. The article demonstrates how impact assessment was shaped during its implementation, supporting the power of dominant groups rather than serving as a procedure to pursue policy coherence.

Another major issue is the CAP's significant impacts on developing countries, particularly in terms of agricultural markets, poverty, and policy coherence for development. **Matthews (2014)** evaluates the 2013 CAP reform, highlighting that while aggregate impacts on world markets are now minor, specific commodities and countries still experience substantial effects, with missed opportunities for more robust global food security and elimination of export subsidies. Another study by **Matthews (2017)** delves into the implications of CAP reforms post-2020, finding that the CAP's effects on the least developed countries are limited and that the focus should perhaps shift to broader poverty alleviation strategies.

Fonseca (2018) discusses how CAP 2014-2020 reforms reduced market distortions but still raise concerns about voluntary coupled support and environmental impacts, suggesting further reforms are necessary for coherence with international climate commitments. The study of **Boysen et al. (2016)** offers new insights into how the CAP affects a developing nation, Uganda, by looking beyond the overall economic effects to examine its influence on poverty. The findings from the simulation suggest that cutting off EU support for agriculture would lead to slight but still beneficial effects on Uganda's economy and its measures of poverty. From the EU's standpoint of adhering to policies that support development, these results back the idea that reducing EU support for agriculture would benefit development.

Furthermore, a series of contributions in the recent scientific literature concern the efficiency of the new EU trade policy strategy, the impacts of EU trade agreements on the agricultural sector and the consequences of the Green Deal from the perspective of a sustainable global food system.

Copenhagen Economics (2016) researchers have studied the impacts of EU trade agreements on the agricultural sector. They claim the EU market is saturated, and 90% of the additional world demand for agri-food products will be generated outside Europe. The Russian ban negatively impacted EU exports, and EU exporters seek new market opportunities. The EU's ambitious bilateral trade agenda is set to continue, with trade agreements creating opportunities for producers and benefiting the EU economy and consumers. However, gains from these agreements should not be taken for granted. This study analysed the EU's trade agreements with Mexico, South Korea, and Switzerland to assess the economic, social, and environmental impacts and identify factors that have fostered and impeded the development of the EU agri-food trade.

The analysis revealed that these trade agreements have increased EU agri-food exports by over 1 billion EUR and increased value added in the sector by 600 million EUR. These agreements have supported nearly 20,000 jobs in the agri-food sector, with 13,700 in primary agriculture. Value added in other sectors has increased by over 400 million EUR, and the agreements have supported an additional 7,700 jobs in the EU. The trade agreements have also increased EU imports and given EU consumers access to cheaper agri-food products. The analysis shows that EU exporters compete more equally against third-country exporters. The EU-Mexico Free Trade Agreement (FTA), which entered into force in 2000, has increased EU exports to Mexico by around EUR 105 million, mainly due to an increased volume of processed agri-food products exported by EU producers before the FTA entered into force. The increase in EU exports to Mexico reflects an increase in total EU exports. The study also found that EU imports from Mexico increased by around 315 million EUR, mainly due to an increased import volume of primary agricultural products imported from Mexico before the FTA entered force. The study suggests that the EU-Mexico FTA could be improved by eliminating specific rates and quotas, increasing its scope, reducing tariff peaks, and solving SPS issues on the Mexican side.

The EU-South Korea FTA, which entered into force in 2011, has reversed the negative trend in the EU's market share in South Korea since 2005. The FTA has increased EU exports to South Korea by around 440 million EUR, mainly due to an increased export volume of primary agricultural products. The increase in EU imports from South Korea has not taken place at the expense of intra-EU trade, and the increased imports have had little impact on production in the EU, taking the absolute value into account. The EU-South Korea FTA supported around 15,000 jobs in the EU agri-food supply chain between 2011-2015, mainly in primary agriculture. The agreement is the most ambitious ever implemented by the EU, and its impact will likely grow in the next decade.

The EU-Switzerland trade agreements have increased EU exports to Switzerland by around 530 million euros, mainly due to an increased export volume of processed agri-food products. The increase in EU imports from Switzerland has not occurred at the expense of intra-EU trade, and the increased EU imports from Switzerland have not impacted agri-food production in the EU. The trade agreements have given EU consumers access to more agri-food products at lower prices, mainly in processed food and beverages. However, the increase in

EU imports is more significant than the increase in exports measured in absolute and relative terms, likely due to non-zero preferential rates on the Swiss side, making EU agri-food products more expensive in the Swiss market.

The EU-Switzerland trade agreements may have evolved over the past 10-15 years, potentially reducing preferential rates and increasing product coverage. The EU agri-food sector can benefit more from completed trade agreements. EU exporters must build reputations and establish distribution networks before entering new markets. Common EU promotion campaigns and targeted export strategies are crucial for Small and Medium Enterprise (SME) exporters. However, EU exporters are not always aware of trade potentials in new agreements, and joint information campaigns can help them anticipate changing business conditions and implement appropriate commercial strategies. The study highlights the potential of exports to Asian export markets, where demand for high-quality agri-food products and limited domestic production capacity offer new business opportunities for innovative EU companies.

Blot and Kettunen (2021) are sceptical about the efficiency of the new EU trade policy strategy, which focuses on supporting sustainable value chains and setting global standards, promoting the green transition through trade. It includes policy initiatives to stimulate greening, such as liberalizing trade in sustainable goods and services and using sustainability standards throughout value chains. The EU is committed to proactively pioneering new international regulations and standards for green and digital transitions with EU standard-setting bodies. However, the success of these initiatives depends on the coherent regime of individual initiatives, which must deliver the best overall outcome for climate and the environment. The strategy does not address the need for synergies between internal and external policies shaping trade and does not address the importance of existing initiatives like appointing a Chief Trade Enforcement Officer (CTEO) and establishing a Single Entry Point (SEP).

Triptolemos.org (2021) has examined the consequences of the Green Deal from the perspective of a sustainable global food system since its potential impact on all links in the food chain makes it potentially very significant. With the aid of 30 researchers from various specialities, it considers not only environmental or economic factors but also cultural, dietary, legal, etc.

The agricultural sector significantly contributes to climate change and can help reduce its impact. The Green Deal aims to address climate change challenges, population growth, and resource scarcity, but it faces socio-economic risks. A prior systematic evaluation of these risks and their impact on economic sectors and consumers is necessary, especially for vulnerable populations. The EU27 has a food energy self-sufficiency of 105%, which could lead to agricultural production turning a low surplus into a deficit. This could increase the need for imports from third countries, which may not follow the principles set by the EU in its Green Deal. The Green Deal may become more of a change in forms than the substance of the European agri-food sector if it only proposes a shift in the production system without considering the quantitative and qualitative aspects of farmers and associated sectors. Europe aims to become a world leader in

sustainability and competitiveness. Still, the European Commission seems overly optimistic in its approaches. Therefore, it is crucial to maintain and increase efforts in research, innovation, and technology transfer to generate new fundamental knowledge about plant and animal physiology, aiming to improve the productivity and resilience of food systems.

The EU is a significant global player in food security matters, with initiatives such as reforming the CAP and the F2F Strategy. The CAP aims to remunerate farmers for providing environmental services and reduce the impact of agrochemicals. The F2F Strategy focuses on a food chain perspective, promoting healthier diets, reducing losses and waste, and applying circular economy and bioeconomy principles. However, it also faces challenges such as the risk of a double food system and the impact on the population, with 17% of the European population living in extreme poverty and 40% being overweight. The COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the importance of a sustainable, robust, and resilient European food system. The Green Deal's measures may severely impact production structures, reducing production and increasing costs and impacting exports and global food security. European foods, known for their safety, nutrition, and quality, now aspire to be the world benchmark for sustainability. However, the environmental ambition of the Green Deal cannot be achieved alone, as climate change and biodiversity loss are global. The Triptolemos Foundation has developed a model for quantifying and analysing the impact of the Green Deal on a sustainable global food system, known as the ITRIn Index.

The CAP has emphasized the need to improve European agriculture's environmental and climate performance, while the Green Deal strategy aims to facilitate the transition towards sustainable food systems, linking all actors in the system. Thus, **Barreiro Hurlé et al. (2021)** have studied the EU's 2030 Climate Target Plan impact assessment using the CAPRI model, which incorporates policies for accelerating the transition towards sustainable food systems. The analysis includes reducing pesticide use, nutrient surplus, organic farming, and high-diversity landscape features. The impacts are modelled under three scenarios: a status quo scenario, assuming no change in the CAP, and a potential implementation of the CAP post-2020 legal proposal. However, the report does not constitute an impact assessment of the strategies, and additional analytical approaches and tools are needed to capture the full potential impacts of the transition.

The potential to further reduce these impacts is underestimated by not considering all initiatives, measures, and resulting synergies covered by the strategies. For example, the shift to organic agriculture could mitigate production reductions, lower livestock production could have less impact on prices and trade, and the positive impact could be enhanced via accelerated technological development and efficiency improvements.

The exercise assumes that the EU acts alone, which could lead to emissions leakage to other world regions. However, non-EU countries have committed to reducing GHG emissions, which could reduce the leakage and negative impacts

for the EU. The report does not provide information on all the benefits derived from those targets for the agricultural sector and broader society.

The analysis on the supply side of sustainable food systems needs improvements to capture the positive feedback in yields from enhanced ecosystem services provided by improved biodiversity. Additional measures could be introduced to reduce the environmental impact of production, minimizing the trade-off between meeting targets and production impacts. The assumptions about the impacts on farm management and yields of the reduction in pesticide use and the increase in organic farming do not capture potential beneficial side effects beyond the agricultural sector, such as health benefits. The Commission's proposal to move from a farm accountancy data network to a farm sustainability data network will help address these limitations. On the demand side, the analysis does not incorporate the ambition related to food waste reduction, the move towards different diets, or the promotion of organic and sustainably produced food. Data availability is an issue that requires cooperation between the retail and processing industries. The Joint Research Centre (JRC) is working to improve knowledge of the effects of measures implemented, develop models to improve the representation of pesticides and organic farming and explore avenues to incorporate the impact of food waste reductions and diet changes. A comprehensive assessment should also incorporate a complete food systems approach incorporating other phases of the food value chain and changes in consumer preferences and behaviour.

The proposed legislative framework for sustainable food systems will necessitate a comprehensive impact assessment to evaluate the EU's agricultural sector's environmental, climate, and health performance. Agro-economic models will be used, but the current approach fails to capture the positive synergies associated with a better environment. The current model focuses on past trade-offs between environmental protection and agricultural production, failing to capture the positive synergies associated with a better environment. Further research and analysis can help improve the model's capacity to capture targets and estimate benefits, highlighting the need for further research and analysis.

The Grain Club has commissioned a study (**Henning and Witzke, 2021**) to analyse the effects of the F2F Strategy on the production, consumption, and trade of relevant agricultural products within the EU. The study shows that the F2F Strategy would lead to a significant decline in production and a respective price increase within the EU, with the reduction of the N-balances by 50% generating the most substantial effects. Compared to the price increase within the EU, the price increases for non-EU countries are much more moderate; in the EU, mineral fertilizer per hectare (ha) and pesticides per ha are strongly reduced by -51% and -58%, respectively. Concerning land use, the implementation of the F2F Strategy, by definition, implies a strong growth of set-aside and ecological priority areas by +11 Million ha. However, implementing the F2F Strategy also implies a transformation of 1.5 Million ha of forest land into Utilized Agriculture Area (UAA).

According to this study, the F2F measures will significantly increase the

ecosystem services of all EU member states and lead to public adjustment costs of approximately 42 billion EUR, of which a significant share would be financed by consumers, in contrast to the farmers' income, which is expected to increase by up to +35 billion EUR. Increasing agricultural income can be explained by the very inelastic demand for agricultural products and the low reactivity of agricultural trading. The F2F adjustment costs are distributed asymmetrically between consumers and farmers and among the farmers themselves; less competitive farms would completely give up production, and more competitive farms survive to collect the higher profits from higher farm prices while exiting farms would realize a loss. In contrast to farmers, agricultural processing industries face a decrease in value-added by the F2F strategy, varying from -0.02% up to -26.9%, depending on the industry. F2F causes food security, poverty, or biodiversity changes in non-EU countries relevant to European society. The most substantial leakage effects can be observed within animal production.

Kornher and von Braun (2020) have analysed the impacts of European agricultural and trade policies on agricultural development and food security in Africa. The growth of African agriculture is significantly less hampered by the current EU agricultural subsidy policy than before the significant elimination of export subsidies and coupled subsidy payments. However, these earlier effects cannot be quickly reversed because agricultural productivity depends on long-term investments in innovation and long-standing favourable framework conditions. A stronger environmental and climate orientation of the CAP is deemed likely and would dampen European agricultural exports to Africa, per the expert consultation conducted for this study. According to the model simulation, food exports from Europe to Africa would fall under the anticipated changes in EU policy. Nonetheless, other exporters would primarily absorb this decline in European exports. The EU ought to increase its investments in the agricultural development of Africa. The EU imposes social and hygiene standards on goods imported into the country and complex rules of origin, which restrict the access of processed products to the EU market, even though exports of raw agricultural materials from Africa are primarily duty-free. Although essential, these standards need to be more openly disclosed. If African standards do not improve, the EU cannot help African nations reach their full export potential.

The EU Green Deal aims to develop an environment-friendly and healthy food system, affecting European producers' competitive position and international trade in foodstuffs. In order to help resolve sustainability issues in trade policy and promote coherence between agriculture, trade, and Green Deal policies, the EU has proposed legislation and other initiatives. Thus, in a recent report, **Matthews (2022)** examines the impact of measures taken to implement this objective in the agri-food sector on developing countries, particularly low-income developing countries, and suggests ways to avoid negative impacts that might hinder their progress toward the UN 2030 SDGs. The French Presidency of the EU Council of Ministers (during the first half of 2022) set priorities to encourage discussions on reciprocal environmental and health standards for European products and imported products, prioritizing the introduction of sectoral mirror

clauses and regulation on deforestation-free imports. These priorities are built on previous EU Trade Policy Reviews and legislative packages for the future CAP. These policies aim to safeguard EU production capacity, avoid off-shore negative environmental consequences, and raise global sustainability standards. Mirror clauses are an example of a unilateral measure, but their use has been discussed mainly at a conceptual level. Choosing the most appropriate trade policy instrument in a specific context should be based on comparing different measures' benefit/risk ratios.

Several policy goals in the EU F2F strategy impact agricultural production within and outside the EU. **Wessler (2022)** discusses the potential effects from an economic angle. By taking into account only partially quantified benefits and costs, he draws on economic evaluations by other authors and discusses their broader implications. Overall, the analyses point to a quantitative decline in EU agricultural production. The F2F strategy harms total consumer surplus and, depending on the underlying assumptions, either causes a net increase or decrease in producer surplus, leading to a net loss in overall welfare. Benefits and costs associated with the F2F strategy's environmental effects, such as those on GHG emissions, biodiversity, or the landscape, are partially quantified. Because of this, policymakers have implicitly determined that the additional net benefits outweigh the reductions in consumer surplus by implementing the strategy. Without additional technological and institutional changes, such as promoting the application of contemporary biotechnology by lowering regulatory barriers, the economic studies combined with studies on the impact of agricultural practices on biodiversity and the emission of greenhouse gases do not support this claim. It is also uncertain whether the majority of consumers will hold this opinion. It is up to EU policymakers to implement the required institutional changes.

Furthermore, **Guyomard et al. (2023)** contend that the new CAP for the 2023-2027 timespan, like its predecessors, will fall short of producing substantial climatic and environmental gains. They demonstrate how the three instruments of conditionality, eco-schemes, and agri-environment and climate measures may have been deployed more consistently and productively in the policy's green architecture. Their recommendations are founded on the fundamental ideas of fiscal federalism and public economics, as well as on agronomy and ecological research findings. The minimum standards that each and every agricultural producer must achieve are known as conditionality criteria. Farmers should be rewarded for efforts that go above and beyond these fundamental needs through eco-schemes for global public goods supplemented by agri-environment and climate policies focused on local public goods. By focusing on permanent grasslands, crop diversity, green cover, and unproductive agro-ecological infrastructures, eco-schemes should span the whole agricultural region. They also talk about the trade-offs that these ideas could cause.

Finally, a group of trade unions, farmers, business owners, engaged citizens, and organizations working in the environment, consumption, development, and research fields have formed the 'Trade Differently' coalition. In one of their articles (**Geurts et al., 2021**), they outline possible scenarios for fair and

environmentally responsible trade policy and the steps that should be taken to achieve them. They also claim that CAP, after 1995, abandoned stable, remunerative prices for agrarian products. This policy has led to overproduction and volatile prices for European farmers. The EU has abandoned supply management for milk and sugar, causing local farmers to suffer while multinational agribusiness profits from low agricultural prices. The EU also uses millions of hectares of land in the Global South to produce luxury products like biofuels, beef, and cattle feed, destroying nature and leading to indigenism and loss of land for small-scale farmers and peasants. The planned reform of the CAP after 2021 presents an opportunity to break with neoliberal aberrations and promote food sovereignty in agricultural trade. This would enable every region, including the EU, to produce food sustainably through its farmers and population.

Producers of perishable plant crops and fishers may unite in producer organizations, preventing monopolies and reducing the difference between consumer and farmer prices. Minimum prices will apply for supermarket products, and 'lowest price guarantees' will be banned. According to these authors, the reform of the CAP should ensure farmers receive prices that cover their costs, allowing for the discontinuation of the current general EU subsidy per hectare. However, farmers who deliver services in line with climate, biodiversity, landscape, and nature objectives will receive cost-covering fees. Product subsidies for cultivating crops with lower selling prices will be implemented, deploying the 59 billion EUR annual CAP budget more effectively. Financial incentives for healthier food will be introduced, such as a national tax on meat and sugar and a 0% VAT tariff on healthy products like vegetables and fruit. If these measures lead to excessive food prices for the poorest, the government will increase social benefits and minimal wages.

3.2 The UN Food Systems Summit

In 2021, the UN convened a Food Systems Summit (FSS) as part of the Decade of Action to achieve the SDGs by 2030. The Summit launched new actions to deliver progress on all 17 SDGs, each of which relies to some degree on healthier, more sustainable and equitable food systems. FSS is a global initiative that aims to address the challenges and opportunities in the food system to ensure food security, sustainability, and human well-being. It is a global platform that brings together governments, international organizations, civil society, the private sector, and academia to share knowledge, expertise, and experiences in addressing the food system's complex issues. The Summit is designed to foster collaboration, innovation, and collective action to transform the food system and achieve the SDGs (**UN Food Systems Coordination Hub, n.a.**).

The five Action Tracks of the Summit are carefully designed to align with the Summit's five objectives. Rather than being separate, each track is intentionally interconnected, allowing for identifying solutions that can deliver broad benefits.

- Action Track 1: Ensuring access to safe and nutritious food for all

- Action Track 2: Shifting to sustainable consumption patterns
- Action Track 3: Boosting nature-positive production at a sufficient scale
- Action Track 4: Advancing equitable livelihoods and value distribution
- Action Track 5: Building resilience to vulnerabilities, shocks and stress

Each action track is led by an expert chairperson and a UN agency, providing a platform for diverse stakeholders to share knowledge, learn from each other, and propose new actions or amplify existing initiatives through public forums, online consultations, and calls for submissions (**European Parliamentary Research Service, 2021; United Nations, n.a.**).

Building on the Innovation Lever of Change, a vital component of the UN FSS, the white paper "Transforming Food Systems: Pathways for Country-led Innovation", published by the World Economic Forum Food Systems Initiative and the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, presents an action-oriented roadmap for countries looking to accelerate and scale inclusive innovation that meet the needs of all stakeholders in the food system and support countries to invest in their capability to innovate (**FAO, n.a.**). The four innovation areas highlighted in the paper include a) Promoting national and regional innovation ecosystems, b) Encouraging societal and institutional innovations, c) Employing and supporting new and existing knowledge and technology, and d) Improving and integrating data and digital systems (**FAO, 2022**).

The EU is well-equipped to influence the global discussion on food systems, having made a significant contribution to the preparations for the United Nations FSS and committing to participate in the follow-up process. The EU's efforts to create a more sustainable food system, as outlined in the European Green Deal and the farm-to-fork strategy, provide a foundation for its engagement in international initiatives. The international cooperation aspects of the farm-to-fork strategy offer a potential opportunity for the EU to participate in global initiatives and share its expertise in shaping a more sustainable food system. Specifically, the EU aims to set a precedent for transformative change by taking the lead in implementing the European Green Deal and the farm-to-fork strategy domestically and globally. Internally, the EU will fully implement its provisions and achieve agreed-upon targets and actions, such as the 2021-2027 action plan on organic farming and the EU Code of Conduct on Responsible Food Business and Marketing Practices. Externally, the EU intends to forge partnerships and alliances, as outlined in the Summit's conclusions, including sustainability clauses in EU trade agreements and establishing a global network to combat food crises (**European Parliamentary Research Service, 2021**).

Formulating country food transition pathways is a complex and multifaceted process, requiring a comprehensive and integrated approach. Critical aspects of this effort include incorporating social, economic, and environmental considerations, aligning policies and incentives, mobilising financial resources, developing human capital and institutional capacity, and creating robust monitoring and evaluation frameworks. A coordinated and collaborative

approach involving multiple stakeholders and disciplines is essential for transitioning to sustainable, resilient, and equitable food systems that meet the needs of a growing global population.

Another critical aspect is the need for policy coherence and alignment across different sectors, including agriculture, health, environment, and trade. This can be achieved by establishing inter-ministerial committees, developing national food policies, and integrating food system considerations into national development strategies. The alignment of policies and incentives can facilitate the creation of an enabling environment that supports the transition towards more sustainable and resilient food systems.

It should be noted that targeted criticism has been addressed toward the FSS. For example, **Canfield et al. (2021)** state that the summit *"...is [...] an effort by a powerful alliance of multinational corporations, philanthropies, and export-oriented countries to subvert multilateral institutions of food governance..."*, noting that *"...the current structure and forms of participant recruitment and public engagement lack basic transparency and accountability, fail to address significant conflicts of interest, and ignore human rights"*, and concluding that the Summit *"...seems to follow a trajectory in which efforts to govern global food systems in the public interest has been subverted to maintain colonial and corporate forms of control"*. In addition, **Montenegro de Wit et al. (2021)** talked about the invention of scarcities and gaps that don't exist, particularly noting that *"...the Summit showcased complex and often contradictory trends..."*, *"...that [the Summit's] 'solutions' continually failed to recognize the reality of small-scale, peasant, and Indigenous food production practices around the world..."*, *"...the rights, agency, and expertise of those who nourish most of the global population were not the foundation of the [Summit's] discourse..."* and that *"The [Summit's] approach was underwritten, above all, by the interests of powerful economic players."* Moreover, **Anderl and Hißen (2024)** note that *"The food sovereignty movement, many non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and eventually scientists, decided to boycott the summit, instead organizing an alternative Peoples' Summit, and withdrawing from long-held institutional roles in the FAO" as "...the circumvention of established institutional mechanisms, and the feeling of betrayal on the side of the movement, was decisive for losing institutional trust"*.

4. SPECIFIC POLICY CASE STUDIES

As mentioned in the first chapter, three policy issues have been identified within the EU's multiplicity of policies enacted or initiated. These policies have been based on their importance for international agricultural trade, although not strictly speaking trade policies. Also, three of the 15 MATS case studies (CS) have been selected to receive feedback on the region or sector-specific impacts of the policies examined.

CS1 on "Reducing poverty among smallholder farmers through enhanced trade regimes and value chains for coffee in Uganda and Tanzania" was selected as the first CS study relevant to two policies, "Organic Certification" on the one hand and "Food Safety Regulations" on the other. The Tanzanian part of the study deals with 150 smallholders and two estates, while in the Ugandan area, the 546 coffee producers of the 2010/11 campaign have increased to 617 in 2015/16 to reach 554 coffee farms in 2019/20.

Uganda was the African country with the most extended area under organic farming, i.e., more than 505,000 hectares, and the largest number of organic producers, with over 404,000 in 2021. Uganda was followed by Ethiopia (over 332,000 hectares) and Tanzania (almost 287,000 hectares). The most important organic crops are cocoa, olives, coffee, nuts, cotton and oilseeds, and the largest part is exported. From 2018 to 2020, African exports increased by almost 60%.

CS4 on "Enhancing Access to Export Markets by Sub Saharan African (SSA) Countries through Sustainable Investments to Ensure Quality and Quality of Agri-food Commodities: The cases of Tanzania, Uganda, Ethiopia, and Ghana" was the second CS study relevant to two policies, "Organic Certification" on the one hand and "Food Safety Regulations" on the other.

The following Table gives a brief description of the CS under study.

Country	Crop/Product/Sector	Region/country		
		Area covered (ha)	No of animals	Nr of Farms
Tanzania	Cassava	990	-	1,900,000 ³
Uganda	Banana	2,300,000	-	766,667 ^{4,5}
Ethiopia	Goats	-	52,500,000 ⁶	11,300,000
Ghana	Cocoa	2,300,000	-	850,000 ⁷

³ [Tanzania: National Cassava Development Strategy \(NCDS\) 2020 – 2030 – Kilimo Kwanza](#)

⁴ With average farm size 1.9 ha

⁵ Kilimo Trust, 2012

⁶ Central Statistics Agency [CSA], 2021

⁷ www.cocobod.gh

Finally, the third CS6, “Analysis of cocoa and chocolate purchasing practices that could undermine living incomes for cocoa farmers” was a sectoral one that analysed the whole cocoa market. So, it concerns about 5 million farmers and 12,100 ha worldwide, while 469,659 ha or 4.0% of the total global area was under organic farming in 2023.

A questionnaire was prepared and sent to project partners of the three CSs to get feedback on the role the specific policy is playing in the CS and the sectors concerned.

The first task of this exercise was to evaluate the specific policies within the framework of the specific CSs concerning their contribution to achieving the relevant Goals and Targets of the Sustainable Development Agenda 2030. The task leaders prepared a list of goals and targets and sent them to the CS-related partners for this purpose. Partners were asked to evaluate the policy according to the following criteria provided by **Griggs et al. (2017)**. Further, more policy-specific questions were posed to elicit the relevant CS information necessary to analyse the results. Finally, policy proposals were provided by CS partners.

4.1 Organic farming certification

Organic farming certification has been selected since, according to the 2023 FIBL (Research Institute of Organic Agriculture) report on organic agriculture worldwide (**Willer et al., 2023**), organic producers reached 3.7 million in 2021 compared to 200,000 in 1999. The countries with the largest number of organic producers in 2023 were India (1,599,010), Uganda (404,246) and Ethiopia (218,175). Since 2020, there has been a 1.7% overall increase in organic area, with an impressive 17.3% in Africa and 5.8% in Asia, while in Latin America, there was a decrease that could be attributed to the decrease in organic rangeland in Argentina. In 2021, 2.9 million metric tons of organic agri-food products were imported to the EU, an increase of 2.8% since 2020.

4.1.1 The policy context

The EU organic farming certification system is linked with international agricultural trade in three ways. It is described in a specific regulation (EU) 2018/848 chapter on organic production and labelling of organic products and repealing Council Regulation (EC) No 834/2007. Accordingly, agrifood products can be imported and traded as organic in the EU if the product complies with the organic farming rules set in the regulation and farmers/processors have been subject to controls by control authorities or control bodies recognised according to a set procedure. These control authorities and/or bodies are recognized as competent to conduct controls in third countries and must provide evidence of their capacity, impartiality and due procedures to fulfil their role. However, there is also the option of organic equivalence. It is a bilateral arrangement between trading partners, recognizing two certification systems as comparable and equally verifiable, allowing for differences (**Jaenicke and Demko, 2015**). Thus, a recognised country is a third country “*which the Union has recognised under a trade agreement as having a system of production meeting the same*

objectives and principles by applying rules which ensure the same level of assurance of conformity as those of the Union." Equivalence is a better option than harmonizing rules and/or regulations since it allows for national/regional adaptations as long as the common objectives are fulfilled and the integrity is assured (**Pekdemir, 2018**). However, up to now, only 14 countries⁸ have this qualification through bilateral agreements, as far as the EU is concerned.

In order to reduce the certification costs for small farmers, both within the EU and for third countries' producers, the EU has introduced in the latest regulation (EU) 2018/848 the possibility for collective certification schemes under the "group certification" title. Starting from 2022, groups of farmers can be certified collectively provided that their members manage land under a specific threshold of size or the individual certification costs are more than 2% of their turnover or standard output and the economic size of their "organic business" does not exceed certain thresholds. Furthermore, the organic farming land managed by farmers-members should be within geographical proximity, a common marketing system should be established among participants, and, finally, the group must "establish a system for internal controls comprising a documented set of control activities and procedures in accordance with which an identified person or body is responsible for verifying compliance with this Regulation of each member of the group". The latter condition is detailed within the same regulation, describing a quite strict "quality assurance" type of scheme.

4.1.2 Impacts on trade

Examining the issue of organic standards and regulation and its effects on organic agriculture trade worldwide, **Vogl et al. (2005)** identify irrefutable benefits derived from the existence of harmonized standards, among others, to increase trust in organic products, facilitation of market access, protection of farmers from unfair competition and consumers from fraud identified. However, they also point out certain caveats, most related to trade and thus are of particular interest in the current discussion. The authors stress the risk of creating new borders and trade barriers while equivalence and harmonization could reduce the leeway for adaptation to local circumstances. Furthermore, discarding local knowledge to homogenise standards under the influence of strong trade partners, i.e., the global North, would provide disincentives for local farmers to innovate to adapt to local circumstances. Thus, valuable local knowledge and experience could be abandoned and lost, and the tendency to cheat increased. The high cost of certification and market access, created by a regulation invasive to the local sociotechnical landscape, could further alienate small farmers from organic and environmentally friendly farming practices. **Vogl et al. (2005)** suggested that harmonisation should not only allow for but should support local adaptations of standards by local farmers' associations. They also suggest the idea of regional standards and quality control systems (recognized by global trade players), with justified differentiation, maintaining their

⁸ Argentina, Australia, Canada, Chile, Costa Rica, India, Israel, Japan, Tunisia, Republic of Korea, New Zealand, Switzerland, United States of America and the UK

effectiveness in withholding organic farming principles but allowing for adaptations to accommodate regional farming systems. A systematic effort to make the most of local knowledge, land use, farming practices, and social norms is necessary to identify innovations that could have a transformative impact.

Pekdemir (2018) stresses the importance of the TBTs and the application of SPS measures of the WTO to provide the context within which organic regulations/laws/standards are made. Their main aim was to ensure non-discrimination and preclude any unnecessary barriers. After a review of the international institutional landscape regarding organic certification, the author concludes that there is a multiplicity of public, private or hybrid certification systems. The lack of a coherent system of mutual recognition creates a fragmented governance system hindering the uptake of organic standards; hence the expansion of organic farming worldwide, since in many cases, transaction, administrative, and other accompanying costs constitute a burden for farmers, especially heavy for small/family farmers.

An important common initiative to disentangle this rather complicated institutional landscape has been the objective of a continuous collaborative project undertaken by the International Federation of Organic Agriculture Movements (IFOAM), United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) and FAO. The creation of an International Task Force (ITF) on Harmonisation and Equivalence in Organic Agriculture from 2003 to 2008, which gave its place to the Global Organic Market Access (GOMA) project, which took place from 2008 up to 2012 resulted in the creation of a benchmark tool for organic standards: Common Objectives and Requirements of Organic Standards (COROS). The process of achieving a common understanding of technical issues concerning the various existing organic certification standards seems to have advanced, as attested by the bilateral agreements signed, e.g., the 14 signed by the EU with third countries. However, apart from the inherently political nature of this process, since it consists only of a broader trade negotiation and agreement, few such agreements have been concluded between developed and developing countries. **Pekdemir (2018)** agrees with the explanation provided by **Bowen and Hoffman (2015)**, who attribute this to the increased need for trust in both parties' technical competence and certification liability. The alternative **Pekdemir (2018)** suggested was to adopt the regionalization of organic standards as a more suitable approach. Regionalisation, in this sense, could take the form of common organic standards and/or equivalence mechanisms or even result in regional agreements involving partners from the public and private sectors of at least two neighbouring countries. The example of the EU organic standards and the benefits of internal organic trade testifies to the success of such an endeavour, even in facilitating trade with third parties.

Apart from decisively promoting intra-regional trade, regional arrangements could enable participant states to negotiate from a better position with significant partners, for example, the EU, in international trade both because of their volume of exports and as a more attractive potential market for exports. Within this context, the author examines, apart from the EU case, six more regional certification initiatives, the East African Organic Products Standard

(EAOPS), the Pacific Organic Standard (POS), the Central American initiative, the Asia Regional Organic Standard (AROS), the African Regional Standard (ARS), and lastly, the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) Standard for Organic Agriculture (ASOA). The EAOPS⁹ project, a continuation of a collaborative effort that started in 1997, was initiated with one of the main objectives being to promote trade with major markets, including the EU, by facilitating market access through negotiating equivalence and/or mutual recognition of the standards. This initiative resulted in a regional organic standard that the IFOAM accepted, but the application to the EU for equivalence was unsuccessful. The need for a competent authority for the correct implementation of the standard was stressed within this process. Nevertheless, steps have been taken by EAOPS as well as POS partners towards this direction, i.e., to introduce certification and labelling arrangements, with the Pacific Partnership (POS) introducing a Participatory Guarantee System to reduce certification costs for farmers.

However, the decision of the EU to demand compliance with the EU rules for non-recognized countries and limit the equivalence process only within the framework of a wider bilateral trade agreement forces certification and control organisations to audit and control for compliance to EU rules in the cases where either no such agreement exists, or no specific reference to equivalence is included, thus generating additional costs for organic farmers and exporters, especially for small scale operations.

In conclusion, in the EU policy context concerning organic certification related to trade, one can comment that the options for promoting organic trade with third parties exist within the regulatory framework and institutional arrangements. Nevertheless, at the same time, the restrictive nature of the existing mutual recognition options and the rigidity of the institutional/operational arrangements do not allow for local/regional adaptation, not even for the rules affecting production practices and, of course, much less, of the organizational prerequisites. Hence, the possibilities of developing countries and many more small/family farms complying with this set of rules/regulations are scant.

4.1.3 EU organic certification policy and its impact on SDGs at the CS's level

It is worth noting that partners from CS4, "Enhancing Access to Export Markets by SSA Countries through Sustainable Investments to Ensure Quality and Quality of Agri-food Commodities: The cases of Tanzania, Uganda, Ethiopia, and Ghana" provided distinct evaluations of organic farming depending on the country and the product in question. This allowed an additional comparison. The entire table can be found in Appendix III, which is attached to this report.

The SDG the EU Organic Farming Policy seems to serve is Goal 10, "Reduce inequality within and among countries". Moreover, within this goal, this policy seems to have a significant contribution to target 10.6, "Ensure enhanced

⁹ Kenya, Tanzania, Uganda, Burundi, Rwanda

representation and voice for developing countries in decision-making in global international economic and financial institutions in order to deliver more effective, credible, accountable and legitimate institutions". Another impressive result is that Goal 12 to "Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns" is the one where EU organic farming certification system contributes to less. It seems that this is because of the widely spread perception (at least among the CS partners) that the EU organic farming policy cancels any effort towards achieving target 12.a "Support developing countries to strengthen their scientific and technological capacity to move towards more sustainable patterns of consumption and production".

One can see that for the CS partners focusing on purchasing practices in the global cocoa/chocolate markets in order to identify risks to undermine the living income of farmers (CS6), the Organic farming policy of the EU is a relatively positive factor in all Goals and Targets that depend on securing a reasonable income for cocoa farmers. On the other hand, for partners focusing on "Reducing poverty among smallholder farmers through enhanced trade regimes and value chains for coffee in Uganda and Tanzania" (CS1), the impact of the EU organic certification scheme and, more specifically, the one that regulates organic imports to the EU, play either an insignificant or enabling role (in the majority of the cases) but not more than that.

Concerning the two most trade-related targets, i.e., 2.b "Correct and prevent trade restrictions and distortions in world agricultural markets, including through the parallel elimination of all forms of agricultural export subsidies and all export measures with equivalent effect, following the mandate of the Doha Development Round" and 2.c "Adopt measures to ensure the proper functioning of food commodity markets and their derivatives and facilitate timely access to market information, including on food reserves, in order to help limit extreme food price volatility" it seems that Organic farming certification as regulated by the EU, has a somewhat positive impact especially in price stabilization.

Finally, an interesting observation is the differences one can see in the evaluation of the partners of the different countries concerning Goal 15 "Protect, restore and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, and halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss". Although most partners agree on the positive contribution of EU organic farming policy towards the sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, the degree of perceived contribution is different.

There seem to be three problems that farmers face when referring to the certification process. The first is that because certification comes from international bodies, partners have identified the risk of a disconnect between the standards/regulations and the local realities. Local conditions, knowledge and experience can be ignored. Furthermore, small producers, often lacking the resources and the capacity, are called to navigate through somewhat burdensome procedures and adopt a new production mentality. The second is the issue of the certification costs, especially for small/family farms. However, it seems that group certification is available and feasible for farmers in all

countries. Finally, although there is an extension service, it is not considered adequate even for conventional farms, much less for organic farms facing specific challenges.

4.2 Food safety regulations

4.2.1 The policy context

Regulation 1107/2009 regulates the placement of Plant Protection Products and the relative active substances in the EU market. According to this Regulation, no Plant Protection Product can be traded and used in any Member State unless the active substance(s) contained have been approved and Maximum Residue Levels (MRLs) are set at the EU level. An MRL is the upper legal level of a concentration for a pesticide residue in or on food or feed set under this Regulation, based on good agricultural practice and the lowest consumer exposure necessary to protect vulnerable consumers according to Regulation 396/2005. This regulation sets the framework for setting MRLs in food and feed. The key aim of the Regulation was to support intracommunity trade in the common market by establishing EU-harmonized MRLs and repealing member-state MRLs. However, when a full MRL is in place at the EU level, this also applies to third-country trade.

According to Reg. 396/2005, an MRL, called Import Tolerance, is set for imported products to meet international trade needs. An Import Tolerance is set when:

- a. The use of the active substance in a plant protection product on a given product is not authorised in the Community for reasons other than public health reasons for the specific product and specific use.
- b. A different level is appropriate because the existing community MRL was set for reasons other than public health reasons for the specific product and specific use.

Hence, one can deduce that an Import Tolerance could be necessary when EU MRLs have not been set for the use of an active substance in a particular crop or set at a level that creates unnecessary obstacles to trade.

Such cases could be when the product or commodity comes from a crop not grown in the EU, and the existing EU MRL does not satisfy importation needs. There is a multiplicity of circumstances that may cause something like that to occur. For example, the MRL may be very low for a specific crop, or the case that an active substance is approved in the EU, but it is not authorized for use on the particular crop or an active substance has been withdrawn and hence not allowed in the EU. Due to the regular review of registered active substances, many substances have been withdrawn from the EU markets in the recent years. Some of the substances have been removed for economic reasons (a small market size for the substance within the EU, in conjunction with the costly re-authorisation process, makes supporting this active substance unviable for a company).

4.2.2 Setting import tolerances

All parties demonstrating a legitimate interest in health, including civil society organisations and commercially interested parties such as manufacturers, growers, importers, and producers of products, can apply to set a specific import tolerance. However, as mentioned by the Commission, "due to the data requirements, especially in cases where the active substance has never been notified or authorised in the EU, it is advisable that the producer of the active substance applies for the import tolerance".

New import tolerances for specific uses not authorised in the EU would require an evaluation of data for the specific use, particularly the residue data relevant to the Good Agricultural Practice of that specific use. The decision here is on a case-by-case basis; however, since it depends on the authorisation status of the active substance concerned, the submission and evaluation of active substance data may also be a prerequisite. No more data is usually required if the active substance has already been approved. If the active substance has been previously approved in Europe, the existing dataset will probably provide much of the information needed, possibly needing updating. If, however, the active substance concerned has never been notified, evaluated or authorised in the EU, a complete dataset on toxicology, methods of analysis, and residue behaviour may be required.

4.2.3 Trade-related issues

Ronen (2017) notes that TBT and SPS measures accompanied the reduction and even elimination of tariffs to provide consumers with an increased level of assurance and more accurate information on the quality and safety of food and agricultural products to, eventually, facilitate trade. At the same time, the most common result of imposing such measures is the introduction of compliance costs that act as import levies. **Ronen's (2017)** review of the relevant empirical literature suggests that TBT and SPS's most probable demand effects are harmful, especially for agriculture and food imports from developing countries. **Disdier et al. (2007)** analysed 43 types of measures (out of 115 possible under the WTO rules) notified to the WTO by importing countries. They conclude that the overall impact of SPS measures and TBT on the trade of agricultural products is negative. However, the exports of OECD countries to other OECD countries cannot be considered significant. On the contrary, they conclude that the exports of developing and least developed countries to OECD countries are significantly reduced. According to the authors, this negative impact is exacerbated when exports from developing and least developed countries to EU member states are considered only.

Furthermore, evidence suggests a robust (**International Trade Center, 2021**) but heterogeneous effect of Non-Tariff Measures (NTMs) such as SPS and TBT on food and agricultural-related enterprises, depending mainly on their size (**International Trade Center, 2015**). Thus, small firms active in food exports face particular problems with testing procedures and lengthy inspections. TBT and SPS measures mainly prevent developing countries' exporters from expanding their target markets (**Ronen, 2017**).

Focusing more on MRLs, there has been a considerable increase in attention paid to the weight of MRLs in the international food and agricultural products trade. **Hejazi et al. (2022)** report a more than fivefold increase in notifications to WTO concerning food safety and animal/plant health regulations between 2000 and 2019. A report by the **Canada Grains Council (2019)** suggests that according to WTO, more than 60% of NTM notifications are related to SPS, while 36% of the latter belong to MRLs. **Ferro et al. (2015)** created a standards restrictiveness index and used data on MRLs for 66 agricultural products from 61 importing countries. They conclude that exporting firms from less and least developed countries face more constraints when stricter MRLs are imposed than exporting firms based in developed countries. The primary purpose of setting MRLs is to protect consumers against harmful substances. Although this process, to be compatible with WTO, has to be based strictly on science and sound risk assessment, non-discriminating, and least trade restrictive, there are strong indications that national administrations tend at the same time to use them as protective towards domestic producers. **Li and Beghin (2014)** attempted to identify and estimate the protectionist element in MRLs by comparing individual national MRL standards with those suggested by the Codex Alimentarius, the latter being used to provide a reference level of a non-protectionist approach.

Furthermore, **Jouanjean et al. (2015)** identified interesting spillover effects of MRL implementation in the United States import regimes since they estimated that the probability of a country experiencing at least one import refusal (due to excess residues) is double if there was a refusal of the same product from a neighbouring country in the preceding year. At the same time, they estimated an increase of 62% in the probability of refusal if a related product was refused from the same country.

4.2.4 Aspects of the EU Food Safety Policy and their impacts on SDGs at the CS's level

The evaluation conducted by the CS partners revealed that the SDG most served by the EU food safety measures applied to imports is Goal 2. "End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture", especially Target 2.4: "By 2030, ensure sustainable food production systems and implement resilient agricultural practices that increase productivity and production, that help maintain ecosystems, that strengthen capacity for adaptation to climate change, extreme weather, drought, flooding and other disasters and that progressively improve land and soil quality." While the Goal which the harmonized system for import tolerances contributes is Goal 1, "End poverty in all its forms everywhere", according to the partners from CS1, the import tolerance system is either insignificant or is a constraint in achieving the target "1.1 By 2030, eradicate extreme poverty for all people everywhere, currently measured as people living on less than \$1.25 a day". And of course, there was a common opinion that the SPS measures applied by the EU are indispensable in order to achieve target 12.4 "By 2020 (2030 now), achieve the environmentally sound management of chemicals and all wastes throughout their life cycle, following agreed international frameworks, and significantly

reduce their release to air, water and soil in order to minimize their adverse impacts on human health and the environment”.

Partners from the CS agree that the existence of a harmonized system of import tolerances as set by the EU facilitates market access and thus promotes sustainable trade, provided, of course, that the information on the specific import tolerance is available and accessible to farmers, especially smallholder farmers.

Partners stress the lack of appropriate extension service as a significant problem, along with more issues identified by the partners of CS1:

- “Limited Access to Information: Farmers may have limited access to information about MRLs and proper pesticide use. Lack of awareness about approved pesticides and their correct application can lead to unintentional violations.
- Inadequate Training and Education: Many farmers may not receive sufficient training on proper pesticide application, safety measures, and the importance of adhering to MRLs. This lack of knowledge can result in the misuse of pesticides, exceeding recommended levels.
- Poor Infrastructure: inadequate infrastructure, including a lack of proper storage facilities and transportation systems, can contribute to the inappropriate handling and storage of pesticides, leading to residue issues.
- Limited Access to Alternatives: Farmers might face challenges accessing and affording safer, alternative pest control methods. Dependence on certain chemical pesticides can increase the risk of exceeding MRLs.
- Lack of Monitoring and Enforcement: Farmers lack effective monitoring and enforcement mechanisms to ensure farmers adhere to MRLs. Without proper oversight, there is a risk of non-compliance going unnoticed.
- Market Access Issues: Farmers might encounter difficulties accessing markets with stringent quality standards. Non-compliance with MRLs can lead to rejected produce, impacting farmers' income and market opportunities.
- Climate Change Effects: Climate change-related challenges, such as unpredictable weather patterns and the spread of new pests and diseases, can complicate pest management strategies, potentially leading to increased pesticide use.
- Financial Constraints: Implementing best practices and acquiring safer pesticides may require financial investments that some farmers cannot afford. This economic barrier can hinder compliance with MRLs.”

4.3 Prospective policies (policies that have recently been enacted or are to be enacted soon)

The EU launched the European Green Deal (EGD) in December 2019 in response to environmental and climate challenges. The EGD is a flagship initiative

comprising various initiatives, strategies, and legislative acts to allow European society and the economy to undergo an equitable, long-lasting, and inclusive transformation. It covers all sectors, including agriculture and food, through the F2F and the EU BDS for 2030. The EGD aims to build a sustainable and healthier food system, impacting the competitiveness of EU producers and international trade in food. The EU has proposed legislative and other initiatives to address sustainability issues in trade policy and promote coherence between agriculture, trade, and Green Deal policies.

4.3.1 Green Deal and Biodiversity Strategy targets

In this part of the paper, the discussion on the effects of possible integration of the Green Deal and BDS elements in currently under negotiation or future trade agreements is going to focus on the restrictions imposed that are directly linked to agricultural production and, at the same time, offer the possibility to draw quantifiable estimations of the impacts.

The first restriction fulfilling these criteria is the target to reduce nutrient losses in EU agriculture by at least 50% without degrading soil fertility. That is translated into reducing fertilizer use by at least 20% by 2030 (**EC, 2020a**).

The second restriction imposed by the F2F Strategy includes two pesticide-related objectives for 2030. The first is to reduce by 50% the overall use of and risk from chemical pesticides, while the second is to reduce by 50% the use of more hazardous pesticides (**European Commission, 2022c**).

Finally, within the BDS for 2030 (**EC, 2020b**), a target to let at least 10% of agricultural area under high-diversity landscape features has been set to allow wild animals, plants, pollinators and natural pest regulators to thrive. Most of these landscape features are unproductive since they include buffer strips, rotational or non-rotational fallow land, hedges, non-productive trees, terrace walls, and ponds.

It is worth stressing that although these targets are under the prospective policies part of the paper, their partial implementation within the CAP strategic plans has already started, either as obligatory prerequisites for farmers to receive CAP payments, e.g., the obligation to leave at least 4% of arable land under landscape features as part of the enhanced conditionality, or as reduction of input use supported by the -newly introduced in CAP strategic plans- ecoschemes (Reg. EC 2115/2020).

4.3.2. The potential effects of Green Deal and Biodiversity 2030 rules' integration in Trade agreements

A series of articles by an experts' team on behalf of the Economic Research Service (ERS) of the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) (**Beckman et al., 2020; Baquedano et al., 2022; Beckman et al., 2022**) have extensively covered the implications of various adoption scenarios on production levels, market prices, trade as well as on welfare, Gross Domestic Product, Land Use, Gross Farm Income (GFI), Food expenditure and finally Food security. For

the study, the authors define a food insecurity indicator as the number of people who lack access to a minimum dietary intake of 2100 kcal daily.

Using the Global Trade Analysis Project – AgroEcological Zones (GTAP-AEZ) model, the authors formulated three scenarios in order to examine the impacts of the adoption of 4 different elements of the subsidies, i.e., 50% pesticide use reduction, 20% chemical fertilizer use reduction, antimicrobial agents use reduction of a 50% and the withdrawal of 10% of the existing agricultural land from productive activities.

Caveats of the approach

In the first of the three scenarios examined, the “EU-only scenario”, EU member states, as expected, adopt and implement the strategies, i.e., the four restrictions mentioned above. At the same time, trade is usually permitted without third parties' obligation to comply with the restrictions. Another scenario is the “global scenario”, where the restrictions are implemented globally as stipulated by the EU initiative. Finally, the “middle scenario” is where only the EU trade partners depend highly on the EU to implement the rules. In this scenario, a simulation of the consequences of non-adoption is a 50% restriction on imports from non-adopting trade partners.

The authors assume that input restrictions would harm production because additional inputs would be used as replacements, affecting resource allocation. Alternatives to chemical inputs were considered limited due mainly to the seasonal unavailability of labour and the lack of qualified managers. Furthermore, the degree of farmers' readiness to transition to alternatives differs highly among products. When discussing possible changes in land management practices that could mitigate the adverse effects on production, the authors argue that no such adaptations are expected for the time horizon they use (8-10 years).

The “EU-only scenario”

Under this scenario, no obstacles arising from policy restrictions are applied to EU imports. Hence, global agricultural production is reduced by only 1%. For all regions but the EU, an increase in agricultural production is estimated to compensate for the 12% decrease in EU production. The reductions per commodity in the EU are more pronounced in the cases of oilseeds, wheat and other crops (-61%, -49% and - 41%, respectively).

A direct consequence of the reduced EU production would be an increase in market prices within the EU, and in most cases, more than 10%. In addition, agricultural commodity prices are predicted to increase in all regions and for almost all commodities, firstly because of the increase in EU prices and global demand for domestic products.

International trade is expected to be reduced by 2%, in the case of the EU-only scenario, due to the dominant position of the EU in the international trade of agrifood products. EU imports are expected to increase, while imports from the EU will decline in almost all regions under this scenario. The relatively more

favoured products would be other crops, wheat and raw milk, with increases of 31%, 18% and 19%, respectively. EU's largest source of imports is Africa (35% of EU imports); hence, exports to the EU from Africa are expected to rise by 103%. Especially for sugar crops, the increase of exports towards the EU is expected to be 143% for African countries, 127% for India, 146% for Mexico and Central America, 349.1% for Middle Eastern and North African countries and an impressive 1060.7% for other South American states.

Regarding the expected impact of GFI, it seems that apart from the EU, where GFI would undergo a reduction of 16.4%, GFI in all other regions is expected to rise. However, farmers in EFTA countries seem to be the primary beneficiaries, with a 25.8% increase, while the increase in Africa, the Middle East and North Africa, and India is expected to be 3.7 %, 2.6% and 5.3%, respectively.

As estimated through the International Food Security Model (**Zereyesus et al. 2023**), food insecurity is defined as the number of people without access to a 2,100 kcal daily intake, a diet necessary to sustain a healthy person. The model generates a baseline against which the impacts of scenarios are assessed. The model in its current state focuses on 83 low- and middle-income countries, and as a baseline in the 2023 edition, it is estimated that in 2023, the food insecure people will be 1.14 billion in the countries covered, which is reduced by 16.8% compared to 2022. The percentage of food insecure population in the 83 low and middle-income countries in focus is estimated to be 26.6%. Finally, under the baseline scenario, 7.9% of these 83 countries' populations are expected to be classified as food insecure in 2033, or 385.9 million persons. That is, a decrease in food insecurity is projected to be 66.1% within the next decade (**Zereyesus et al., 2023**).

Against this optimistic baseline scenario, the EU-only scenario would result in a 0.5% increase in the number of food insecure people in 77 countries, mainly in Africa and other Asian countries, by 0.4 % and 1%, respectively.

The "Middle scenario"

This scenario consists of expanding the above restrictions to regions outside the EU. Namely, EFTA countries, other European countries, Turkey, Ukraine, the Middle East, North Africa, and Africa would adopt the restrictions under this scenario. That is, regions that either depend on exporting food and agricultural products to the EU or have a strong colonial past. For the rest of the regions, the model assumes the imposition of a 50% import restriction by the EU (**Beckman et al., 2020**).

Global production is estimated to present an overall decrease of 4%. The impact, of course, is not equally distributed among the various regions. EFTA, Middle East, and North African countries are estimated to observe a 15% decline in production. Both these regions are considered adopters under the Middle scenario. Regions' non-adopters also, under this scenario, would face a reduction in food and agricultural production, albeit smaller. The authors attribute this reduction to the reliance of non-adopter countries on trade with adopters.

As far as market prices are concerned, in adopter regions, prices are estimated to increase by at least 50%, while in specific commodities, mainly primary products such as crops, are expected to present a 3-digit increase. The authors attribute it to the two elements of the scenario, that is, the reduction of inputs for adopters and the trade restrictions for non-adopters. The decrease in the value of agricultural trade worldwide, if the middle scenario were to be implemented, is estimated to be 9%. GFI is expected to decrease in non-adopting regions, while the inverse is estimated in adopting regions due to the abovementioned price increase. Food expenditure per capita seems to increase by an average of \$159, mainly to adopter countries, while, according to the estimations of the model, food expenditure decreases in most non-adopting regions.

Regarding the impacts on food security, in the case of partial adoption of the restrictions, the authors predict a 2.2% increase in the food-insecure population due to the predicted increase in food prices.

Using a more elaborated version of the partial implementation scenario, based on game theory, **Beckman et al. (2022)** assume that regions that use smaller amounts of inputs than the ones imposed by the Green Deal (that is, 20% less fertilisers and -50% pesticides) will not face any impact on their production process but have to adopt the trade restrictions of the EU. This exercise resulted in more modest impacts on the global market impacts, namely global prices, output and trade.

The global scenario

Finally, the most “ambitious” scenario taken into account by the team in the ERS of the USDA was the global scenario, according to which the restrictions proposed by the EU Green Deal would be adopted globally.

Under this scenario, the researchers estimate a reduction of 11% in global agricultural production, although the impacts on individual global regions differ significantly. Thus, Ukraine, the former USSR and other European countries will face more considerable impacts, while Latin America (Mexico, Central America and South America, excluding Argentina and Brazil) will see a significant reduction. It is worth noting that the latter regions under the middle scenario would not suffer any adverse effects. The Middle East and Africa are also estimated to suffer significant decreases but slightly less than in the middle scenario.

As far as prices are concerned, there is an apparent expectation that prices will rise globally under this extreme scenario, with the “Former USSR and rest of Europe” region expected to have 3-digit increases and crops like rice, wheat and coarse grain facing the highest increases worldwide. Trade is also estimated to be reduced by 4% globally; however, according to the authors, the Middle East and Africa are estimated to have significant increases in their crop exports, while the picture is not that clear in the case of Latin America.

Moving to food expenditure and food security, it seems that expenses for food will significantly increase globally (\$450). In contrast, the estimated increase is

even greater than the global average in Africa, the Middle East, the former USSR, the rest of Europe, and Latin America. Hence, the impact of global adoption of the restrictions proposed by the EU Green Deal is estimated as severe since there is an increase of 185 million people in the insecure population, which can be translated to a 3.9% increase in the prevalence of food insecurity worldwide. It also seems that Africa and Other Asia are the regions expected to be more affected, with an estimated increase of 80 and 72 million food insecure populations, respectively.

Regional distribution of impacts

Baquedano et al. (2022), elaborating further on the expected impact on 77 low and middle-income countries due to a hypothetical global adoption of the EU Green Deal restrictions, suggest that the expected improvement in global food security is going to be hampered by a 3.7% up to 2030. This negative outcome was estimated to be more pronounced in Sub-Saharan Africa, with a hindrance of 5.4% on average (10.5% in Southern Africa), 6.2% for Central America and the Caribbean and an impressive 12.3% in Other Asia¹⁰. However, as the authors advise, the results should be treated with reservation since the proposal's specifics are unclear, not even for European farmers, much less how it could be implemented in the case of global adoption. Furthermore, the study mentioned does not account for investment in technology and innovation and their rate of acceptance by farmers, especially for the time scope of the study.

4.3.3. The expected effects of the F2F Strategy on the production, consumption, and trade

The effects of the F2F Strategy on the production, consumption, and trade of relevant agricultural products within the EU have been analysed in the study of **Henning and Witzke (2021)**. The analysis was carried out using the CAPRI model, a regionalized partial equilibrium model centred on the agricultural sector, and it considered the effects of farm production on the environment and land use. The CAPRI sector model is connected to an international trading model considering global trade flows and their effects on agricultural prices. The trading model is based on the new trade theory, which holds that traded agricultural commodities are imperfect substitutes rather than perfectly homogeneous goods. As a result, trade in agricultural commodities has non-linear transaction costs and trade flows.

This study reveals that a decrease in European agriculture production reduces net exports by the EU, particularly for cereals and beef. If all F2F measures are implemented simultaneously, the EU net export position for these products would revert to a net import position. However, this would only apply to poultry, while the net milk export would remain unchanged. The net export of pork would also be reduced, and the respective net import values for cereals and beef would

¹⁰ Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Bhutan, Brunei Darussalam, Burma, Cambodia, Indonesia, Laos, Macau, Malaysia, Maldives, Mongolia, Nepal, North Korea, Pakistan, Philippines, Sri Lanka, Thailand, Timor Leste, Vietnam

increase. The welfare effects of the F2F Strategy depend on the responsiveness of agricultural trading. Increased responsiveness of agricultural trading implies a fundamental redistribution of adjustment costs between farmers and consumers and significantly increased leakage-effects. The price, trade balance, and welfare effects depend on including the European agricultural market in international agricultural trade. If perfect responsiveness is assumed, the costs of implementing the F2F Strategy would be borne by farmers, leading to a more considerable reallocation of production and additional GHG-emissions in non-EU countries. Reducing European meat consumption significantly reduces leakage effects, while reducing general food waste in European food supply chains can positively impact leakage effects. Including agriculture in CO₂-allowance trading increases the climate efficacy of the F2F Strategy.

In addition, according to this study, the EU's F2F measures were ad hoc and lacked a specific scientific foundation. The Green Deal's goals include reducing nitrogen pollution, climate neutrality, and conserving biodiversity. Agricultural production, or rather consumption of agricultural goods, plays a crucial role in achieving these goals. Current agricultural production and consumption patterns do not align with the Green Deal's objectives and require adaptation. A common European agricultural framework is needed to achieve these modifications.

The study has also identified several key issues that the F2F Strategy has to address. Firstly, it is ineffective in reducing climate change, particularly regarding GHG emissions. The strategy should promote technological progress in the agricultural sector to minimize leakage effects, reduce food waste, and avoid production shifts to non-EU countries. Secondly, it should include the LULUCF-Sector (Land-Use, Land-Use Change, and Forestry), which accounts for 48% of the compensation for the F2F-induced reduction of GHG emissions in agriculture. Controlling LULUCF effects in the EU is relatively easy through regulatory measures and proven incentives for land-use change. Thirdly, the strategy's actions should be goal-oriented, with political restrictions targeting ecosystem services provided by agriculture. Lastly, the strategy needs to ensure a socially just distribution of adjustment costs, ensuring that all member states implement all cornerstones and that costs and benefits are distributed fairly among farmers and consumers. Further research is needed to identify adequate indicators and incentive schemes for effective public management of biodiversity. Finally, the Green Deal goals require smart and innovative governance mechanisms.

4.4. EU internal policies under the light of the "Policy Coherence for Development" principles

According to Article 208 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union: *"The Union shall take account of the objectives of development cooperation in the policies that it implements which are likely to affect developing countries."*

This obligation of the EU is the legal basis of the self-imposed task to assess all policies that can affect developing countries regarding their compliance with Policy Coherence for Development principles. In the Better Regulation Guidelines (2021 edition), policymakers are requested to analyse the specific impacts of the

proposed initiative on external aspects of the EU's internal policies. Thus, in the 2023 edition of the Better Regulation toolbox of the European Commission (EC),¹¹ there is an explicit reference to the obligation to assess all internal EU policies and initiatives, focusing on their potential impacts on third countries. Furthermore, a specific "Tool" is assigned to integrate the SDGs into the assessment.

Blanco (2018), in her study on the impact of CAP on developing countries, refers to an initial impact assessment that took place during the preparation of the policy proposals for the CAP's 2014-2020 programming period. However, it states that, unlike the detailed assessment of the internal impacts of CAP proposals, their impact on third countries was mainly based on existing evidence. Consequently, the review concluded in a rather vague way, stating that no clear outcomes have been identified regarding CAP proposal impacts on developing countries, invoking the heterogeneity of the countries in question (net food exporters/importers, rural/urban populations, etc.).

Since its inception in the second half of the 20th century, CAP has been accused of a policy with severe trade-distorting effects. This was true up to the late 1990s, given the existence of import tariffs, export subsidies, and production-coupled subsidies on the one hand and the prevalence of the EEC, EC and EU as a trading partner in the global trade arena on the other. Production-coupled subsidies were acting as incentives for the production of subsidized products. Combining that production boost with export subsidies leads to surpluses, directly competing with developing countries in export markets due to their artificially low prices. At the same time, the imposition of import tariffs created a situation where developing countries' exports to the EU constantly depended on preferential access arrangements with the EU (**Boysen et al., 2016**).

However, the wide application of preferential access status to an array of countries, especially the "Everything But Arms" (EBA) status for Least Developed Countries (LDC), established by the EU, as well as the fact that food security in developing countries net food importers improved due to EU policies, shed a different light to the discussion. According to existing literature, as reviewed by **Blanco (2018)**, the eventual impacts of the various CAP policy tools on developing countries depend highly on their status as importers or exporters concerning the commodities included in the CAP protective regimes. Furthermore, their trade relationship with the EU is an equally important factor, considering that there are several types of preferential access to the EU without the burden of the high import tariffs. More specifically, 47 Least Developed Countries (LDCs) enjoy duty-free and quota-free EU market access under the Everything But Arms (EBA) initiative. A further 77 African, Caribbean and Pacific (ACP) countries have already signed a Partnership Agreement (Cotonou agreement), and seven more groups of ACP countries are negotiating or have even agreed on Economic Partnership Agreements. Another issue worth considering when assessing the impacts of internal EU policy measures on trade

¹¹ Better regulation: guidelines and toolbox (europa.eu) accessed June 2024

partners, especially from the Global South, is identifying the populations under poverty affected by the specific measures, i.e., rural or urban. Finally, agricultural and market structures and the existence, size, and strength of regional/national value chains are other important factors to consider (**Blanco, 2018**).

During the years, starting in 1992 with the McSharry reform, in anticipation, among other reasons, of the 1995 WTO agreement, a process of decoupling subsidies from production has started. During these years, with the consecutive reforms of the CAP, export subsidies have been abolished except for crisis circumstances, and decoupling subsidies from production has been completed. Hence, the trade-distorting character of the CAP has been reduced considerably (**Blanco, 2018**), although there were some remnants of production-coupled subsidies. Examples of these remnants are the Voluntary Coupled Payments introduced in 2014-2020 and reinforced with the current 2023-2027 framework, as well as a special aid to specific crops such as cotton for four EU MS, namely Bulgaria, Greece, Spain and Portugal.

In the rest of this chapter, two different elements of the CAP are going to be examined, focusing on the impacts of these elements on trade, especially in developing countries, including LDCs: (a) payments decoupled from production such as the single farm payment or as it is currently called Basic Income Support for Sustainability, where farmers are paid an annual support per eligible hectare, and (b) coupled income payments (previously called Voluntary Coupled Support) where MS are allowed to support specific sectors, and/or productions and/or types of production in order to maintain production levels (including the crop-specific payment for cotton).

The choice was to focus on these CAP tools since the other two, namely (c) Market-related measures again for specific sectors and finally (d) rural development measures, exert an influence similar to the one by decoupled payments in the sense that they act as an incentive for production since they play a role in the maintenance of marginally viable sectors and products and encourage investment (**Blanco, 2018**).

(a) Decoupled income support

The shift in EU CAP from subsidies linked to production to decoupled payments was completed with the 2003 mid-term review aimed at reducing the market distortion effects of the CAP. Halting the function of EU payments as incentives for production was also thought to reduce significantly the trade distortion effects, which was one of the main arguments against the 20th century CAP, especially its adverse impact on rural livelihoods in LCDs. Nevertheless, many experts suggest that income support, albeit not linked to production, may influence farmers' decisions and, thus, indirectly affect production. This could be attributed, according to the review performed by **Blanco (2018)**, to the income effect (since EU farmers are willing to produce even if the prices are not adequate, as they complement their income with the aid), to an incentive for farm investments as well as a less risk averting behaviour on the part of the farmers due to the relative stability offered.

Evidence from empirical studies suggests that the combination of decoupled support and trade restrictions at the borders harms imports from third countries. **Boysen et al. (2016)**, focusing on Uganda, suggest that eliminating EU decoupled support would benefit Uganda's economy, albeit to a small degree, since it is highly dependent on agricultural exports. **Urban et al. (2016)**, in a work that tries different levels of "decoupling" of decoupled payments, i.e., explores possible capitalization paths of decoupled payments, suggest that removal of the single farm payment would result in a more pronounced decrease of production in labour and capital intensive sectors and products, therefore developing countries relying more on such crops (e.g., vegetables and fruits) would benefit more by possible removal of decoupled support. On the other side of the spectrum, the effects of a possible abolishment of EU internal support on net-importing developing countries are estimated to benefit the trade balance since producers gain and exports increase. Still, consumers are affected by increased global food prices. Hence, food security seems negatively influenced, especially for the urban population.

(b) Coupled income support

As mentioned above, two types of subsidies are linked to production. The first is the Voluntary Coupled Support (VCS) offered to a series of sectors/products, and the second is a special crop support scheme for cotton. There is no empirical evidence for the impacts of implementing the specific types of subsidies, but one can resort to research conducted for similar kinds of subsidies and reasonably extrapolate the results.

As far as the VCS is concerned, it was introduced during the 2014-2020 programming period. During that period, VCS could go up to 8% of the national ceiling for direct payments, although this could reach 13% in some instances, plus an additional 2% for protein crops.

All other MS have decided to implement this voluntary scheme except for Germany. The total number of measures under this scheme was between 250 and 260 (2022), and the annual budget allocation has been around 4.2 billion € or 11.2% of the direct payments budget. The animal sectors, i.e., milk and milk products (21.4%), sheep and goat meat (12.8%) and beef and veal (38.8%) received 72.9% of all coupled support, while as far as the area-based VCS are concerned, protein crops (11.3%), fruits and vegetables (4.5%), and sugar beet (4.3%) have been the main receivers of VCS (**EC, 2022d**).

Currently, VCS has been replaced by Coupled Income Support (CIS) in the form of an annual payment per hectare, or animal is intended to help the supported sectors and productions or specific types of farming overcome pressures by improving their competitiveness and/or sustainability and/or the quality. However, MS are free to support protein crops without having to base their decision on the difficulties encountered.

The 18 sectors under consideration are cereals; oilseeds; protein crops, including legumes and mixtures of legumes and grasses provided that legumes remain predominant in the mixture; flax; hemp; rice; nuts; starch potatoes; milk and

milk products; seeds; sheep and goat meat; beef and veal; olive oil and table olives; silk worms; dried fodder; hops; sugar beet, cane and chicory roots; fruit and vegetables and short rotation coppice.

Around 21% of EU farms are expected to receive some coupled payment in all MS except from the Netherlands. It accounts for 12% (23.031 billion €) of the Direct Income Support for the five years of implementation. Wallonia, Lithuania, Poland, Portugal, France, and Latvia allocate more than 10% of their total budget to CIS (**Chartier et al., 2023**).

Moving to the crop-specific support for cotton, four countries are entitled to such support: Bulgaria, Greece, Spain, and Portugal. A base area is indicated for each MS: Greece 250,000 ha, Spain 48,000 ha, Bulgaria 3,342 ha and Portugal 360 ha. Fixed yields and suggested payments per ha are mentioned; hence, the total amount per MS is fixed. If an MS exceeds the base area, a proportional reduction of the per hectare payment is imposed (Reg 2115/2021).

(b).1. Production-linked support and its effects on developing countries

Specific references are made to three products/sectors receiving coupled support due to the important repercussions for developing countries: milk and milk products, sugar, and cotton.

a. Milk and milk products

Since first implemented in 2015, VCS for milk and milk products has been selected by 19 MS, and 32 measures have been applied until 2022 (**EC, 2022d**). While the CIS option in the new programming period (2023-2027) appeared, it has been taken up by 21 MS applying for 45 different interventions (**EC, 2022d**). The allocation reached 896 million € in 2022 (21.4% of the total VCS budget and 2,4% of the annual ceiling for direct payments) with an average of 78 €/head payment in 2022.

Fat-filled milk powder is a novel product in which vegetable fats replace animal fats, producing it cheaper than conventional products. Evidence suggests (**Korhher and Von Braun, 2020; Matthews and Soldi, 2019**) that exports of fat-filled milk powder have increased, which directly affected traditional milk-producing African countries like Uganda, Niger, and South Africa, which although having an increased number of animals, their average yield is considerably lower than the European. Producer prices in both continents are similar, but since transportation costs for milk powder are low, the CIF price of milk is not significantly higher and, in some cases (e.g., Mali and Ethiopia), lower than the local producers' price. Moreover, due to structural deficiencies, African countries could not meet domestic demand for milk, and a reduction in EU exports could pose a food security threat for Africa. A literature review by the authors suggests that coupled payments tend to increase the production and productivity of EU dairy farms, thus affecting exports to Africa. Complementary to direct payments, the EU implements price stabilization measures, i.e., purchasing milk powder when the prices are too low. This measure reduces disincentives to EU investments in dairy production and artificially reduces world market prices when the stocked milk powder is sold, directly affecting African exporters of milk, e.g.,

Uganda. However, it improves the situation for urban consumers in import-dependent countries, e.g., in North and West Africa (**Korhher and Von Braun, 2020**).

b. Sugar beet sector

More than 60% of EU sugar imports come from ACP and LDC countries under preferential access regimes. However, following the general trend of EU sugar imports, these imports tend to decrease due to lower EU prices, rendering the EU a net exporter of sugar. On the other hand, since first implemented in 2015, VCS for sugar beet has been selected by 11 MS, and 12 measures have been applied up to 2022 (**EC, 2022**). The allocation reached 181 million € in 2022 (4.3% of the total VCS budget and 0.5 % of the annual ceiling for direct payments) with an average of 357 €/ha payment (ranging from 100 to 600 €/ha) in 2022, covering 507,669 ha. A significant increase in the area covered with sugar beet in 2017 could be attributed to the high level of support, which was expected to continue (**Blanco, 2018**).

c. Crop – Crop-specific Subsidy for Cotton

According to FAO's Agricultural Outlook 2021-2030 (**OECD, n.a.**), Sub-Saharan African cotton accounts for 15% of global exports. The area under cotton has been expanding during the last decade, except in 2020, when a decline in world market prices led to a drop, especially in Mali. Many countries in SSA virtually export all their cotton produce since spinning mill consumption is limited in the region. Finally, regional exports were projected to increase by 2.7% annually.

As mentioned above, four EU countries are entitled to apply a subsidy to cotton production, limited by a fixed ceiling per MS. **Gilson et al. (2004)** report that US and EU subsidies reduce the world price of cotton and consequently the income of developing countries, particularly LDCs that are depending on cotton for their foreign exchange earnings. For four West African countries (Benin, Burkina Faso, Chad and Mali), cotton represented 20–44 percent of total merchandise exports in 2001-3 (**Baffes, 2003**). Furthermore, **Gilson et al. (2004)** suggest that the share of EU export subsidies in the total may not reflect the impact of these subsidies on developing countries, particularly on West and Central African cotton producers, because the production in Greece and Spain directly competes with developing countries' production in global markets with the EU subsidies per unit of production being the highest in the world. According to **Baffes (2003)**, abolishing all global market distortions could result in a 70% decrease in EU cotton production.

5. CONCLUSION, DISCUSSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Policy coherence and sustainability issues in EU trade-related policies

The awareness of the problems caused by modern agrifood systems has led to efforts to transition to sustainable food systems. This transition is also necessitated by the COVID-19 crisis and the war in Ukraine, which have exposed vulnerabilities in agricultural and food systems.

The EU is crucial in promoting a transition to sustainable and resilient food systems, with its ambitious Green Deal and global role in agri-food markets. Trade agreements and bilateral cooperation offer opportunities to achieve sustainability standards with partner countries. The Green Deal strategy aims to facilitate the transition towards sustainable food systems, as outlined in the F2F and Biodiversity Strategies. In order to help resolve sustainability issues in trade policy, a diverse range of policy areas must be aligned. In addition, a series of policy contradictions, inconsistencies, and trade-offs must be overcome in seeking coherence between agricultural, environmental, and trade policies.

Scholars are cautious about the efficiency of the new EU trade policy strategy, which focuses on supporting sustainable value chains and setting global standards, promoting the green transition through trade. It includes policy initiatives to stimulate greening, such as liberalizing trade in sustainable goods and services and using sustainability standards throughout value chains. The strategy does not address the need for synergies between internal and external policies shaping trade, nor does it address the importance of existing initiatives like appointing a Chief Trade Enforcement Officer and establishing a Single Entry Point.

The Green Deal's measures may severely impact production structures, reducing production, increasing costs, and impacting exports and global food security. However, the environmental ambition of the Green Deal cannot be achieved alone, as climate change and biodiversity loss are global.

Concerns have arisen that the F2F Strategy may lead to off-shoring food and agricultural production overseas, potentially undermining policy objectives. Also, the F2F adjustment costs are distributed asymmetrically between consumers and farmers and among the farmers themselves; less competitive farms would completely give up production, and more competitive farms survive to collect the higher profits from higher farm prices while exiting farms would realize a loss. In contrast to farmers, agricultural processing industries face a decrease in value-added by the F2F strategy. F2F causes changes in food security, poverty or biodiversity in non-EU countries that can be considered relevant to European society. The most substantial leakage effects can be observed within animal production.

The F2F Strategy does not yet correspond to a consistent agricultural policy strategy, as individual measures are specific production restrictions that do not provide a consistent framework for implementing the Green Deal's goals in

agriculture. The literature has identified several key issues that the F2F Strategy has to address: (i) it is ineffective in reducing climate change, particularly regarding GHG emissions; (ii) it should include the LULUCF-Sector (Land-Use, Land-Use Change and Forestry), which accounts for 48% of the compensation for the F2F-induced reduction of GHG emissions in agriculture; (iii) the strategy's actions should be goal-oriented, with political restrictions targeting ecosystem services provided by agriculture; (iv) the strategy must ensure a socially just distribution of adjustment costs; (v) finally, the Green Deal goals require smart and innovative governance mechanisms that combine market flexibility and planning security with regulatory policy interventions.

Legal basis, political commitment, and demand from civil society exist for the EU trade relations in general, and its bilateral trade agreements in particular, to support the achievement of the SDGs internally and deliver sustainability globally. However, recent studies show that the EU generally outsources economic, social and environmental impacts abroad, notably through trade. There is, therefore, an urgent need to make EU trade and its impacts on global value chains more sustainable. Improving EU FTAs regarding the scope of their sustainability commitments and monitoring and enforcement mechanisms is a crucial part of that objective as they encompass a large share of EU trade.

We have examined EU trade agreements regarding including sustainability-related policies within agricultural trade. This examination concerns all the agreements and political initiatives that make up the 'core' trade policy of the EU, i.e., the 44 "Agreements in place" involving 77 countries/regions and the 5 "Agreements being adopted or ratified" involving 25 countries/ regions. A central part of our study involved identifying provisions in the trade agreements under consideration, focusing specifically on the agricultural trade/sector concerning sustainability aspects.

A few trade agreements consider agriculture's environmental impact in their provisions. These agreements include issues such as a) the impact on soil and water quality, b) soil erosion and pollution by agricultural chemicals, c) the management of impacts through the use of antibiotics and decontaminants, d) conservation and sustainable use of biological diversity, and e) genetically modified organisms. It should also be noted that the trade agreements include climate/climate change-related provisions in several cases. However, there is no mention of the agricultural trade or the sector.

5.2 Policy proposals

5.2.1 EU Organic Farming Certification Scheme

The issue raised by the CS partners but also proposed as prominent by the relevant literature is the decision of the EU not to proceed to the solution of equivalence but rather to impose the procedure of individual recognition of control and auditing organisations as almost the only solution for countries wishing to export their organic produce to any EU country. Formal recognition and encouragement of regional organic standards, such as the East African

Organic Products Standard (EAOPS), the Pacific Organic Standard (POS), the Central American initiative, the Asia Regional Organic Standard (AROS), the African Regional Standard (ARS), and lastly, the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) Standard for Organic Agriculture (ASOA) would be a crucial step towards that direction.

On the other hand, countries having a vested interest in the promotion of their organic exports, for example, countries where organic farming is increasing rapidly and can be an essential factor in alleviating poverty and setting the basis of sustainable growth of their agriculture, could increase their efforts to cooperate effectively among them and the private sector, involving all relevant stakeholders in order to promote the idea of regional standards, better adapted to the local circumstances, adopting effectively local practices.

Adopting group certification could solve the second issue raised, i.e., the certification costs. Promoting such efforts, especially those under participatory certification schemes, could also contribute to fulfilling the need for adaptation to local circumstances. According to **Willer et al. (2023)**, there are 323 Participatory Guarantee Schemes in 76 countries, with more than 1.4 million farmers involved (more than 1.3 million certified) managing 887.744 hectares of land. Many of these initiatives are encountered in Africa, Asia, and Latin America, and the number of initiatives involving farmers and areas covered increases yearly.

5.2.2 Harmonised Food safety regulations for EU imports

An increase in resources dedicated to research in order to find alternative methods to pesticides would contribute to a reduction of the need for their use. An essential part of the funds targets such goals within the EU research framework. An increased effort towards research focusing on phytosanitary issues prevalent in developing countries could significantly contribute to this direction.

Systematically taking stock of local practices, knowledge, and experience, utilising current technologies, and creating knowledge bases accessible to farmers and practitioners in developing countries would be other vital steps.

5.2.3 Agricultural Extension and Training

The literature and all partners' responses stressed the importance of reinforcing and reforming the Agricultural Extension service towards an integrated knowledge management system with access to research results, information and all available IT (Information Technology) methods and equipment.

5.3 Policy coherence and impacts of CAP elements on third countries

The introduction of decoupled subsidies by the EU has significantly decreased the trade effects of the CAP, hence the CAP's impact on developing countries. However, decoupled payments can still negatively influence the Global South since they act as a production incentive for the EU farmers. Empirical evidence

corroborates this result, especially for net-exporting developing countries and/or the rural livelihoods of net-importing developing countries.

Coupled subsidies for the milk sector, combined with market intervention, tend to increase EU milk production, and the use of an innovative technology for the production of milk powder exerts pressures on world milk prices as well as on African countries' exporters of milk. However, an abrupt decrease in EU milk powder exports could threaten food security in import-dependent countries of Africa.

Coupled subsidies can incentivize the expansion of sugar beet cultivation. This could result in a further reduction of EU sugar imports from developing countries. The crop-specific subsidy for cotton of the EU can have a highly distorting effect on the global export market, even more significant than its share in the global subsidies implies. Countries depending on cotton to increase their exports, like Sub-Saharan African countries, are more affected by the distortions created.

In conclusion, the consecutive CAP reforms completed the shift towards area-based payments, which increased the coherence of the specific EU policy with the EU's global development goals. However, in some cases, the continuation and expansion of coupled payments do not seem to comply with the Policy Coherence for Development principles.

5.4 General policy-making recommendations

In order to increase the coherence of EU policies with the SDGs and draw from the Better Regulation Toolbox 2023, one can formulate some general suggestions for the EU policy-making process.

When an initial but careful screening of policy proposals suggests that there will be significant impacts on developing countries, the overall stakeholder consultation process should be adapted to include stakeholders in developing countries. If this consultation reveals that the impacts could be significant, the external dimensions of the policy have to be focused since the beginning of the process. Anyway, the EPA and ACP states oblige the EU to inform them in advance of its intentions to take any measures that might affect them. The CARIFORUM-EU Economic Partnership Agreement contains a similar obligation regarding bananas, rice, rum and sugar (**Endres and Endres, 2017**).

Due to the high heterogeneity of developing countries in all aspects (social, political, and economic), an impact assessment should be made on a case-by-case basis. However, priority should be given to LDCs.

More specifically, drawing from **Endres and Endres (2017)**, the screening process should inquire whether the products covered by the proposal are also produced in developing countries, particularly LDCs and other countries most in need. At the same time, a possible high dependence of one or more countries on a specific product for their exports is an important issue.

5.5 Considerations concerning TBTs and SPS

Concerning specific issues like the TBTs and the SPS, a general suggestion could be that it is important to consider the impact on developing countries. Such requirements and regulations usually prominently affect developing countries, particularly least developed countries, as they often lack the awareness or capacity to identify and comply with them.

Furthermore, before suggesting TBTs and/or SPS, one should demonstrate that the requirements are proportionate to the objectives pursued. If, in particular, trade is affected on SPS grounds, a proper risk assessment should be conducted based on sound scientific evidence.

It is strongly suggested that existing international standards, guidelines, and recommendations be referred to. Any regulation beyond these reference texts should be based on sound science.

Control, inspection and approval procedures should be clear and known in advance to partners. Any change should be clearly communicated in advance. It is recommended that special procedures and rules should be applied to developing countries in order to facilitate compliance.

New regulations should not constitute obstacles that make developing countries' preferential access to the EU market impossible. For example, costs imposed by new SPS erode their competitiveness due to the preferential status because adjustment costs are usually much higher and even prohibitive for firms in developing countries. A study like this could be significant for LDCs and other developing countries, which depend on a few export commodities since they could be affected gravely by the new regulation imposed. Particular attention should be paid to vulnerable groups and/or areas within developing countries, such as the rural and urban poor.

5.6 Policy recommendations emerging from Policy Briefs of the MATS project's Case Studies

Apart from the case study-related policy recommendations derived in this task, a set of policy recommendations have been identified and presented through other activities of the MATS project. In specific, recommendations have been presented in the Policy Briefs of case studies 1, 14, and 15 (<https://sustainable-agri-trade.eu/policy-briefs/>), as well as in the reports of case studies 1, 3 and 15 (available at: <https://sustainable-agri-trade.eu/case-study-reports/>). The proposed policy recommendations from these four case studies address a wide range of themes, as presented grouped -per topic- below. The policy recommendations are also available per each case study in Appendix IV.

Economic and financial aspects

- Revive and empower farmer cooperatives;
- Implement tailored risk management programs for smallholder farmers;

- Policy reforms favouring cooperatives' sustainability;
- Provide adequate financial support to enhance regulatory capacity and enforcement mechanisms;
- Recognize family labour within fair trade certification;
- Revise and operationalize the related policies to address the constraints affecting effective and profitable participation of smallholder farmers;
- When comparing carbon tax imposed on industries versus establishing carbon tax on dairy trade, at least in terms of emissions, it may be more efficient to impose regulations directly on the industry;
- Reformulate the Common Agricultural Policy such that, instead of granting the hectare and animal-based support, the support would be based on the environmental and climate protection measures in peat lands, carbon farming in mineral lands, animal welfare measures, using low-emission feeds and by applying precision farming;
- Understand the interest and direction of China's policies in future imports;
- Adopt gradual and integrated trade-related measures that align with the dimensions of economic instruments and land regularization;
- Revise free trade agreements to ensure a more balanced and fair relationship;
- Provide targeted financial and public policy support to small-scale food producers to enable the spread of agroecological practices;
- Address unequal support challenges by advocating for a fairer distribution of agricultural subsidies and assistance between European and North African countries;
- Strengthen the negotiating capacity of North African countries by forming a unified platform for agricultural trade negotiations with the EU.

Environmental aspects

- Environmental performance-based subsidies may be an option in the future instead of area and animal-head-based subsidies;
- Reformulate the Common Agricultural Policy such that, instead of granting the hectare and animal-based support, the support would be based on the environmental and climate protection measures in peat lands, carbon farming in mineral lands, animal welfare measures, using low-emission feeds and by applying precision farming;
- Eradicate illegal deforestation;
- Include other wooded lands and natural grasslands in the future revision of the EU Regulation on deforestation-free products;
- End support for the expansion of unsustainable monocultures;

- Promote the adoption of water preservation techniques and sustainable irrigation systems as well as the use of less water-intensive, locally-adapted varieties;
- Increase transparency around water use rights and allocation and strengthen participatory water governance systems;
- Use tools such as the 'water footprint' to measure the trade in embedded water resources;
- Develop standards and norms, drawing on indigenous knowledge, local plant varieties and animal breeds, and local consumer preferences.

Societal aspects

- Recognize family labour within fair trade certification;
- Ensure transparent pricing that accounts for labour inputs;
- Educate farmers on fair trade principles and negotiation skills;
- Advocate for supportive policies to protect labour rights;
- Foster community dialogue to integrate fair labour practices;
- Incorporate fair treatment of family labour into certification requirements;
- Support strategies focused on establishing a national public system for socio-environmental traceability;
- Address power imbalances by involving civil society in the negotiation process and establishing mechanisms for monitoring sustainability outcomes;
- Recognize and address the role of women in the agricultural sector by instituting gender-sensitive policies and promoting women's empowerment;
- Ensure adequate working conditions and remuneration for farmworkers;
- Defend the rights of farmers and agricultural workers to organize and ensure their voices are influential in regional policy discussions;
- Protect small-scale food producers' rights to land, water, seeds and plant genetic resources.

Policy and regulatory aspects

- Policy reforms favouring cooperatives' sustainability;
- Revise and operationalize the related policies to address the constraints affecting effective and profitable participation of smallholder farmers;
- Address the disconnection between producing and consuming countries through coherent, reformed, and supportive international policy agenda;

- Provide adequate financial support to enhance regulatory capacity and enforcement mechanisms;
- Reformulate the Common Agricultural Policy such that, instead of granting the hectare and animal-based support, the support would be based on the environmental and climate protection measures in peat lands, carbon farming in mineral lands, animal welfare measures, using low-emission feeds and by applying precision farming;
- When comparing carbon tax imposed on industries versus establishing carbon tax on dairy trade, at least in terms of emissions, it may be more efficient to impose regulations directly on the industry;
- Environmental performance-based subsidies may be an option in the future instead of area and animal-head-based subsidies;
- Include other wooded lands and natural grasslands in the future revision of the EU Regulation on deforestation-free products;
- Adopt gradual and integrated trade-related measures that align with the dimensions of economic instruments and land regularization;
- Partner with regional organizations to develop a food sovereignty strategy, promoting local production and self-sufficiency;
- Adopt the 2016 Policy Recommendations of the UN Committee on World Food Security to enact public policies to support local, national, and regional food systems;
- Assert the same right to a just transition for agriculture in North Africa as in Europe;
- Urge Europe to cease its support for austerity policies in North Africa.

Technical aspects

- Implement tailored risk management programs for smallholder farmers;
- Reequip agricultural extension service providers with modern working tools that can assist them in operating in a digitized agricultural world;
- Create smallholder farmer's awareness about available agribusiness-based digital services and improve physical infrastructure development for digital access and lower costs associated with access to the internet and digital devices;
- Promote the adoption of water preservation techniques and sustainable irrigation systems as well as the use of less water-intensive, locally-adapted varieties;
- Use tools such as the 'water footprint' to measure the trade in embedded water resources;
- Agricultural extension services provide farmers with the training and resources needed for sustainable agricultural practices.

Organizational aspects

- Synergy and integration among the various levels of the value chain actors;
- Public and private partnerships established by the local government;
- Support strategies focused on establishing a national public system for socio-environmental traceability;
- Partner with civil society and research institutions;
- Bolster the capacity of North African nations in agricultural research, innovation, and technology transfer;
- Strengthen the cooperative sector and enhance the representativeness within cooperative membership.

5.7 A short discussion

Following up on the information presented in the earlier sections, we will touch briefly on a few additional issues noted in the literature concerning the observations and recommendations provided by MATS Case Studies partners in this section.

Engaging various stakeholders, including civil society organizations, is crucial for achieving policy coherence. **Holden (2019)** discusses how interactions between EU institutions and civil society can shape trade policy, yet such engagement often faces institutional resistance and limited influence. This is also suggested in all CSs in various ways, e.g., in CS15: *“Partner with civil society and research institutions”, “Foster Agricultural Research Partnerships”, and CS1: “Public and private partnership should be established by the local government.”*

As **Matthews (2020)** points out, the CAP has traditionally focused on agricultural productivity and market stability, which can conflict with the SDGs' broader sustainability and social goals. Current CAP legislation fails to fully integrate the SDGs, lacking a measurable framework to assess its contributions to these goals. A relevant reference is made in CS14: *“Support strategies focused on establishing a national public system for socio-environmental traceability.”*

Another theme that should be highly prioritized during food systems transformation is a just transition to sustainability. Ensuring that no one is left behind or pushed behind in the shift to low-carbon and environmentally sustainable economies and societies is a broad definition of a just transition. This may make it possible to take more ambitious climate action and give the SDGs more momentum (**UN, 2023**). Similarly, in CS15, it is recommended: *“Invest in Agroecology to Support a Just Agricultural Transition”, and “Assert the same right to a just transition for agriculture in North Africa as in Europe”.*

The Green Deal goals require smart and innovative governance mechanisms that combine market flexibility and planning security with regulatory policy

interventions (**Henning and Witzke, 2021**). Likewise, **Glass and Newig (2019)** emphasize the importance of governance mechanisms such as participation, policy coherence, reflexivity, adaptation, and democratic institutions in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals. Their study underscores the need for inclusive and adaptive governance structures to ensure that policy coherence is effectively pursued in the context of sustainable development. Also, **Holden (2019)** explores the interactions between EU institutions and civil society organizations, highlighting the need for constraining market forces and promoting regulatory global governance to achieve SDGs. Relevant to these findings is the CS1 recommendation: *"Provide adequate financial support to the Tanzania Coffee Board (TCB) to enhance its regulatory capacity and enforcement mechanisms. Invest in capacity building, foster partnerships, advocate for policy reforms, explore innovative financing mechanisms, and implement robust monitoring and evaluation systems."*

Henning and Witzke (2021) point out that tradable allowances (emissions trading systems) for CO₂ emissions in the non-agricultural sector are promising tools for monitoring ecosystem services like N-balance and biodiversity. These systems also allow for a flexible and transparent division of costs between farmers and consumers and between individual social groups. In a similar line of reasoning, CS3 partners argue that:

- *"When comparing carbon tax imposed on industries versus establishing carbon tax on dairy trade, at least in terms of emissions, it may be more efficient to impose regulations directly to the industry."*
- *Instead of carbon taxing, it may be more efficient to reformulate the CAP such that, instead of granting the hectare and animal-based support, the support would be based on the environmental and climate protection measures in peat lands, carbon farming in mineral lands, animal welfare measures, using low-emission feeds and by applying precision farming."*
- *Instead of area- and animal head-based subsidies, environmental performance-based subsidies may be an option in the future."*

In analysing the impacts of European agricultural and trade policies on agricultural development and food security in Africa, **Kornher and von Braun (2020)** found that low-cost food imports have hampered the growth of competitive agricultural production and, over time, undermined the agricultural sectors of African nations. Because agricultural productivity depends on long-term favourable framework conditions and long-term investments in innovation, these earlier effects cannot be quickly reversed. The suggestion of CS15: *"Forge a North African Trade Coalition - Strengthen the negotiating capacity of North African countries by forming a unified platform for agricultural trade negotiations with the EU"*, could be a step toward creating competitive agricultural sectors in Africa.

Effective monitoring mechanisms are essential for ensuring policy coherence. **Weiß (2021)** emphasizes the need for enhanced monitoring by the European Parliament to ensure that trade policies, including those related to agriculture,

align with non-trade policy objectives and the SDGs. However, current monitoring frameworks are often insufficient. In CS15, it is recommended: *"Establish mechanisms for monitoring sustainability outcomes."*

Finally, the CS15 partners' proposal: *"Develop a food sovereignty strategy - Work with regional organizations to develop a food sovereignty strategy, promoting local production and self-sufficiency"*, highlights the varied and nuanced approaches to the concept of food security. As **Candel et al. (2014)** stress: Inductive frame analysis reveals that the consensus frame of food security can be broken down into six conflicting and overlapping sub-frames: (1) the productionist frame, (2) the environmental frame, (3) the development frame, (4) the free trade frame, (5) the regional frame, and (6) the food sovereignty frame. During the CAP reform debates of 2009–2012, the productionist and environmental frames were used the most frequently. In contrast, the European Commission simultaneously used multiple frames in its communications. Therefore, due to these various framings of the relationship between the CAP and food security, a clear political vision of this relationship is lacking.

5.8 Overall suggestions

To summarize all the above, the following overall suggestions are made to ensure EU policies are coherent with the SDGs:

1. Develop a holistic approach to policy-making: Integrate the various dimensions of sustainable development at all policy-making stages, considering the synergies and trade-offs between economic, social, and environmental policy domains.
2. Establish a framework for tracking progress: Develop a set of indicators to monitor and evaluate the coherence of EU policies with SDGs.
3. Promote policy coherence through regional differentiation: Consider the regional differentiation of impacts on food security, income, prices, and trade volume when developing policies.
4. Enhance cooperation between institutions: Strengthen coordination and integration among different EU institutions and agencies to ensure policies align with SDGs.
5. Develop evidence-based policies: Use quantitative and analytical abilities to find and evaluate synergies and trade-offs between policy alternatives.
6. Involve stakeholders in the policy-making process: Engage with civil society, industry representatives, and other stakeholders to ensure their concerns and interests are considered in policy development.
7. Monitor and evaluate the impact of EU policies on SDGs: Conduct regular assessments of the impact of EU policies on SDGs, using indicators such as those developed by the OECD, to identify areas for improvement.

8. Provide targeted support for small-scale food producers: Support small-scale food producers through targeted financial and public policy support, enabling them to adapt to changing market conditions and promote sustainable agriculture practices.

9. Develop capacity-building programs for developing countries: Provide capacity-building programs for developing countries to help them develop sustainable agriculture practices and improve their competitiveness in global markets.

10. Strengthen dispute settlement mechanisms: Establish effective dispute settlement mechanisms in EU trade agreements to ensure that disputes are resolved fairly and transparently.

These mechanisms aim to promote coherence between EU policies and the SDGs by integrating sustainability considerations into policy-making, enhancing cooperation between institutions, and involving stakeholders in the policy-making process.

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APPENDIX I: TARIFF QUOTAS

A tariff quota allows for the duty-free or reduced-rate importation of a certain amount of a commodity, while any quantities imported in excess of the quota are subject to a higher duty rate. Tariff quotas approved on the basis of Article 31 of the Treaty of the Functioning of the EU constitute an exception to the normal state of affairs since they permit, during the period of validity of the measure and for a limited quantity, the total (total suspension) or partial waiver (partial suspension) of the normal duties applicable to imported goods (antidumping duties are not affected by these suspensions).

In the framework of several agreements that the EU has concluded with third countries/territories and autonomous preferential arrangements for some beneficiary countries/territories, **tariff concessions** are provided for a pre-determined volume of goods. These tariff concessions are called 'preferential tariff quotas'. Within these **preferential tariff quotas**, a predetermined volume of goods originating in a specified country/territory can benefit at import into the Union from a more favourable duty rate than the normal third countries/territories duty mentioned in the combined nomenclature.

Entitlement to benefit from preferential tariff quotas is subject to the presentation of the necessary evidence of origin.

Nevertheless, products originating in Western Sahara subject to controls by customs authorities of the Kingdom of Morocco shall benefit from the same trade preferences as those granted by the European Union to products covered by the Association Agreement.

Autonomous tariff quotas

As stated already for suspensions, for some economic sectors, it is necessary to stimulate competition by low tariffs, as we find in numerous industrial sectors.

Their role is to stimulate the economic activity of Union industries, improve competitive capacity, create employment, modernise structures, etc.

They are normally granted to raw materials, semi-finished goods or components not available in the EU (suspensions) or which are available but in insufficient quantities (tariff quotas), **but no tariff quotas are granted for finished products.**

A request to open an autonomous tariff quota may be presented as such or result from the examination of a suspension request. In this connection, account will be taken, where appropriate, of consequential damage to any new production and manufacturing capacity, which could be made available in the Union or a third country/territory with preferential tariff arrangements.

When identical, equivalent or substitute products are manufactured in sufficient quantities within the EU or by producers in a third country/territory with preferential tariff arrangements, the granting of a quota is normally excluded. The same applies where the measure could result in a distortion of competition regarding the final products.

Council Regulation 2021/2283 opening and providing for the management of autonomous tariff quotas of the Union for certain agricultural and industrial products (Official Journal L 458 of 22.12.2021, p.33) establishes the list of goods subject to these measures. It is regularly amended (in January and July each year) to consider new requests presented by the Member States.

Information on the products currently examined by the Commission with the aid of the Economic Tariff Question Group.

More information and forms concerning autonomous tariff suspensions and quotas can be found in the Commission Communication (Official Journal C 363 of 13.12.2011, p.6).

Council Regulation (EU) 2020/1706 of 13 November 2020 opening and providing for the management of autonomous Union tariff quotas for certain fishery products for the period 2021-2023 (Official Journal L 385, 13.11.2020, p. 3), establishes the list of fishery products subject to autonomous tariff quotas.

Management

The Commission's Directorate-General manages most tariff quotas and is responsible for the Taxation and Customs Union on a 'first-come, first-served' basis, irrespective of where the goods are imported into the EU. The legal provisions governing the management of these tariff quotas are contained in Articles 49 to 54 of the Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2015/2447 of 24 November 2015, which lays down detailed rules for implementing certain provisions of the UCC.

Information about the current balances of those tariff quotas, managed on a first-come, first-served basis, is available [on-line](#).

Agricultural

Some tariff quotas are managed by the Commission's Directorate-General, responsible for Agriculture and Rural Development through a system of import licenses. Various Council and Commission Regulations contain specific provisions for managing these tariff quotas.

APPENDIX II: EU TRADE AGREEMENTS: PROVISIONS ON AGRICULTURAL TRADE/SECTOR IN CONNECTION TO SUSTAINABILITY ASPECTS

Country/ies	Document	Article	Title	Text
Agreements in place				
Albania	Stabilisation and association agreement between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Albania, of the other part	Article 95	Agriculture and the agro-industrial sector	Cooperation between the Parties shall focus on priority areas related to the Community acquis in the field of agriculture. Cooperation shall notably aim at modernising and restructuring the Albanian agriculture and agro-industrial sector, and at supporting the gradual approximation of Albanian legislation and practices to the Community rules and standards.
Algeria	Euro-Mediterranean association agreement between the European Community and its Members States, of the one part, and the People's Democratic Republic of Algeria, of the other part	Article 58	Agriculture and fisheries	Cooperation shall be aimed at the modernisation and restructuring, where necessary, of the agriculture, forestry and fisheries sectors. It shall in particular be aimed at: support for policies geared to developing and diversifying production; food security; integrated rural development, including improvement of basic services and development of ancillary economic activities; promoting environmentally-friendly forms of agriculture and fisheries; the evaluation and rational management of natural resources; establishing closer relations, on a voluntary basis, between enterprises, groupings and professional organisations representing the agricultural, fisheries and agri-business sectors; technical assistance and training; harmonising phytosanitary and veterinary standards and checks; cooperation between rural areas, exchange of experience and know-how on rural development; support for privatization; the evaluation and rational management of fish stocks; support for research programmes.
Andorra	Agreement in the form of an exchange of letters between the European Economic Community and the Principality of Andorra	-	-	No specific provision on agricultural trade/sector in connection to sustainability aspects
Antigua and	Economic Partnership	Article 37	Agriculture and	1. The Parties agree that the fundamental objective of this Agreement is

<p>Barbuda, Bahamas, Barbados, Belize, Dominica, Dominican Republic, Grenada, Guyana, Jamaica, St Kitts and Nevis, St Lucia, St Vincent and the Grenadines, Suriname, Trinidad and Tobago (CARIFORUM States)</p>	<p>Agreement between the CARIFORUM States, of the one part, and the European Community and its Member States, of the other part</p>		<p>fisheries - Objectives</p>	<p>the sustainable development and the eradication of poverty in CARIFORUM States, and the smooth and gradual integration of these economies into the global economy. In the agricultural and fisheries sectors, this Agreement should contribute to increasing the competitiveness of production, processing and trade in agricultural and fishery products in both traditional and non-traditional sectors, between the Parties, consistent with the sustainable management of natural resources.</p> <p>4. The Parties recognise that ensuring food security and enhancing livelihoods of rural and fishing communities are critical elements of the eradication of poverty, and the pursuit of sustainable development. They consequently recognise the need to avoid major disruption of markets for agricultural, food and fish products in CARIFORUM States.</p>
<p>-//-</p>	<p>-//-</p>	<p>Article 43</p>	<p>Agriculture and fisheries - Cooperation</p>	<p>1. The Parties acknowledge the importance of the agricultural, food and fisheries sectors to the economies of CARIFORUM States and of cooperating to promote the transformation of these sectors, with the aim of increasing their competitiveness, developing their capacity to access high quality markets and in view of their potential contribution to the sustainable development of the CARIFORUM States. They recognise the need to facilitate the adjustment of the agricultural, food and fisheries sectors and the rural economy, to the progressive changes brought about by this Agreement, while paying particular attention to small scale operations.</p> <p>2. Subject to the provisions of Article 7, the Parties agree to cooperate, including by facilitating support, in the following areas:</p> <p>(c) Compliance with and adoption of quality standards relating to food production and marketing, including standards relating to environmentally and socially sound agricultural practices and organic and non-genetically modified foods;</p>
<p>Armenia</p>	<p>Partnership and cooperation agreement between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of</p>	<p>Article 53</p>	<p>Agriculture and the agro-industrial sector</p>	<p>The purpose of cooperation in this area shall be the pursuance of agrarian reform, the modernisation, privatisation and restructuring of agriculture, the agro-industrial and service sectors in the Republic of Armenia, development of domestic and foreign markets for Armenian products, in conditions that ensure the protection of the environment, taking into account the necessity to improve security of food supply as</p>

	Armenia, of the other part			well as the development of agri-business, the processing and distribution of agricultural products. The Parties shall also aim at the gradual approximation of Armenian standards to Community technical regulations concerning industrial and agricultural food products including sanitary and phytosanitary standards.
Azerbaijan	Partnership and cooperation agreement between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Azerbaijan, of the other part	Article 54	Agriculture and the agro-industrial sector	The purpose of cooperation in this area shall be the pursuance of agrarian reform, the modernisation, privatisation and restructuring of agriculture, the agro-industrial and service sectors in the Republic of Azerbaijan, development of domestic and foreign markets for Azerbaijani products, in conditions that ensure the protection of the environment, taking into account the necessity to improve security of food supply as well as the development of agribusiness, the processing and distribution of agricultural products. The Parties shall also aim at the gradual approximation of Azerbaijani standards to Community technical regulations concerning industrial and agricultural food products including sanitary and phytosanitary standards.
Bosnia and Herzegovina	Stabilisation and association agreement between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and Bosnia and Herzegovina, of the other part	Article 95	Agriculture, and the agro-industrial sector	Cooperation between the Parties shall focus on priority areas related to the Community acquis in the field of agriculture and veterinary and phytosanitary domains. Cooperation shall notably aim at modernising and restructuring the agriculture and agro-industrial sector in Bosnia and Herzegovina, in particular to reach veterinary and phytosanitary Community requirements and at supporting the progressive approximation of the legislation and practices of Bosnia and Herzegovina to the Community rules and standards.
Botswana, Eswatini, Lesotho, Mozambique, Namibia, South Africa (SADC)	Economic Partnership Agreement between the European Union and its Member States, of the one part, and the SADC EPA States, of the other part	Article 68	Cooperation on agriculture	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The Parties underline the importance of the agricultural sector to the SADC EPA States for food security, generating rural employment, increasing incomes of farm households, creating an inclusive rural economy, and as a basis for wider industrialisation and sustainable development, as well as to contribute to the objectives of this Agreement. 2. The use of export subsidies on agricultural goods in the trade between the Parties shall not be allowed from the date of entry into force of this Agreement. 3. An agricultural partnership is established between the EU and the

				SADC EPA States to facilitate an exchange of views between the Parties on agriculture, inter alia, food security, development, regional value chains and integration. The coverage of issues and operational rules for the agricultural partnership shall be established by common agreement of the Parties acting within the Committee referred to in Article 103.
Cameroon	Economic Partnership Agreement between the European Community and its Member States, of the one part, and the Central Africa Party, of the other part	ANNEX I	2. Agriculture and food safety at regional level	2.1. Support for improving productivity (seed programme, research and dissemination); 2.2. Development of agro-industries; 2.3. Improvement in trade in agricultural products; 2.4. Support for the implementation of a regional common agricultural policy
Canada	Comprehensive Economic and Trade Agreement (CETA) between Canada, of the one part, and the European Union and its Member States, of the other part	-	-	No specific provision on agricultural trade/sector in connection to sustainability aspects
Chile	Agreement establishing an association between the European Community and its Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Chile, of the other part	Article 24	Cooperation on agriculture and rural sectors and sanitary and phytosanitary measures	<p>1. Cooperation in this area is designed to support and stimulate agricultural policy measures in order to promote and consolidate the Parties' efforts towards a sustainable agriculture and agricultural and rural development.</p> <p>2. The cooperation shall focus on capacity-building, infrastructure and technology transfer, addressing matters such as: (a) specific projects aimed at supporting sanitary, phytosanitary, environmental and food quality measures, taking into account the legislation in force for both Parties, in compliance with WTO rules and other competent international organisations; (b) diversification and restructuring of agricultural sectors; (c) the mutual exchange of information, including that concerning the development of the Parties' agricultural policies; (d) technical assistance for the improvement of productivity and the exchange of alternative crop technologies; (e) scientific and technological experiments; (f) measures aimed at enhancing the quality of agricultural products and supporting trade promotion activities; (g) technical assistance for the strengthening of sanitary and phytosanitary</p>

				control systems, with a view to supporting as far as possible the promotion of equivalence and mutual recognition agreements.
Colombia, Ecuador, Peru	Trade Agreement between the European Union and its Member States, of the one part, and Colombia, Ecuador and Peru, of the other part	-	-	No specific provision on agricultural trade/sector in connection to sustainability aspects
Comoros, Madagascar, Mauritius, Seychelles, Zimbabwe (ESA)	Interim Agreement establishing a framework for an Economic Partnership Agreement between the Eastern and Southern Africa States, on the one part, and the European Community and its Member States, on the other part	ANNEX IV	DEVELOPMENT MATRIX (a) Agriculture and Livestock	Promote sustainable agriculture, improve production, productivity and diversification, develop agro-industry, trade, and ensure food security Activities could be: (i) Development of harmonised regional policies, legal and regulatory frameworks, Standards and Quality Assurance and certification instruments accredited to international standards and capacity building on sustainable production systems. (ii) Construct and improve irrigation facilities and infrastructure, rural infrastructure linking production areas to markets, cold storage chains and related infrastructure. (iii) Promotion of Agricultural/Livestock R&D and its implementation; gender mainstreaming in access to production factors; strengthening of the value chain and technology transfer. (iv) Development of special vehicle insurance schemes and instruments for access to finance. (v) Establish and strengthen institutions to promote modalities of disease handling, implement national and trans-boundary disease control programme and establishment of national and regional early warning systems and centres of excellence for agricultural workers.
Costa Rica, El Salvador, Guatemala, Honduras, Nicaragua (Central America)	Agreement establishing an Association between the European Union and its Member States, on the one hand, and Central America on the other	-	-	No specific provision on agricultural trade/sector in connection to sustainability aspects
Côte d'Ivoire	Stepping stone Economic Partnership Agreement between Côte d'Ivoire, of the one part, and the European Community and its Member	-	-	No specific provision on agricultural trade/sector in connection to sustainability aspects

	States, of the other part			
Egypt	Euro-Mediterranean agreement establishing an association between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Arab Republic of Egypt, of the other part	Article 50	Agriculture and fisheries	Cooperation shall be aimed at: (a) the modernisation and restructuring of agriculture and fisheries, including: the modernisation of infrastructures and of equipment; the development of packaging, storage and marketing techniques; the improvement of private distribution channels; (b) the diversification of production and of external outlets, inter alia, through the encouragement of joint ventures in the agri-business sector; (c) the promotion of cooperation in veterinary and phytosanitary matters and in growing techniques, with the objective of facilitating trade between the Parties. In this regard, the Parties shall exchange information.
Faroe Islands	Agreement between the European Community, of the one part, and the Government of Denmark and the Home Government of the Faroe Islands, of the other part	-	-	No specific provision on agricultural trade/sector in connection to sustainability aspects
Fiji, Papua New Guinea, Samoa, Solomon Islands (Pacific)	Interim Partnership Agreement between the European Community, of the one part, and the Pacific States, of the other part	-	-	No specific provision on agricultural trade/sector in connection to sustainability aspects
Georgia	Association agreement between the European Union and the European Atomic Energy Community and their Member States, of the one part, and Georgia, of the other part	Article 333	Agriculture and rural development	Cooperation between the Parties in the field of agriculture and rural development shall cover, inter alia, the following areas: (a) facilitating the mutual understanding of agricultural and rural development policies; (b) enhancing the administrative capacities at central and local level to plan, evaluate, implement and enforce policies in accordance with EU regulations and best practices; (c) promoting the modernisation and the sustainability of the agricultural production; (d) sharing knowledge and best practices of rural development policies to promote economic well-being for rural communities; (e) improving the competitiveness of the agricultural sector and the efficiency and transparency for all stakeholders in the markets; (f) promoting quality policies and their control mechanisms, including geographical indications and organic

				farming; (g) wine production and agro tourism; (h) disseminating knowledge and promoting extension services to agricultural producers, and (i) striving for the harmonisation of issues dealt within the framework of international organisations of which both Parties are members.
Ghana	Stepping stone Economic Partnership Agreement between Ghana, of the one part, and the European Community and its Member States, of the other part	-	-	No specific provision on agricultural trade/sector in connection to sustainability aspects
Iceland, Liechtenstein, Norway	Agreement of the European Economic Area, Main Part	-	-	No specific provision on agricultural trade/sector in connection to sustainability aspects
Iraq	Partnership and cooperation agreement between the European Union and its Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Iraq, of the other part	Article 90	Cooperation on agriculture, forestry and rural development	The objective is to promote cooperation in the agriculture, forestry and rural development sectors with a view to promoting diversification, environmentally sound practices, sustainable economic and social development and food security. To this end the Parties will examine: (a) capacity building and training to public institutions; (b) measures aimed at enhancing the quality of agricultural products, capacity building measures for producers associations and supporting trade promotion activities; (c) environmental health, animal and plant health measures and other related aspects, taking account of the legislation in force for both parties, in compliance with WTO and multilateral environmental agreement rules; (d) measures relating to sustainable economic and social development of rural territories, including environmentally sound practices, forestry, research, transfer of know-how, access to land, water management and irrigation, sustainable rural development and food security; (e) measures relating to preservation of agricultural traditional

				knowledge that give their populations their specific identities, including cooperation on geographical indications, exchanges of experiences at local level and development of cooperation networks; (f) modernisation of agricultural sector including farming practices and diversification of agricultural production.
Israel	Euro-Mediterranean agreement establishing an association between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the State of Israel, of the other part	Article 46	Agriculture	The Parties shall focus cooperation in particular on: support for policies implemented by them to diversify production; promotion of environment-friendly agriculture; closer relations between businesses, groups and organisations representing trades and professions in Israel and in the Community on a voluntary basis; technical assistance and training; harmonisation of phytosanitary and veterinary standards; integrated rural development, including improvement in basic services and development of associated economic activities; cooperation among rural regions, exchange of experience and know-how concerning rural development.
Japan	Agreement between the European Union and Japan for an Economic Partnership	Article 19.1	COOPERATION IN THE FIELD OF AGRICULTURE ARTICLE - Objectives	The Parties recognise that promoting trade in agricultural products and foods between them is in their mutual interest, and aim at promoting cooperation on sustainable agriculture, including rural development and the exchange of technical information and best practices for providing safe and high quality foods for consumers in the European Union and Japan.
-//-	-//-	Article 19.2	COOPERATION IN THE FIELD OF AGRICULTURE ARTICLE - Scope	1. The Parties shall cooperate in the areas referred to in Article 19.1 in accordance with their respective laws and regulations. The Parties shall encourage and facilitate cooperation among relevant groups, entities, competent authorities and other organisations of the Parties. 2. The scope of cooperation referred to in paragraph 1 shall cover: (a) the promotion of trade in agricultural products and foods, including a dialogue on the relevant regulation; (b) cooperation with a view to improving farm management, productivity and competitiveness, including the exchange of best practices regarding sustainable agriculture, as well as the use of technology and innovation; (c) cooperation on production and technology in agriculture and foods;
Jordan	Euro-Mediterranean agreement establishing an	Article 71	Agriculture	The Parties shall focus cooperation in particular on: support for policies implemented by them to diversify production; promotion of

	association between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan, of the other part			environment-friendly agriculture; closer relations between businesses, groups and organisations representing trades and professions in Jordan and in the Community on a voluntary basis; technical assistance and training; harmonisation of phytosanitary and veterinary standards; integrated rural development, including improvement in basic services and development of associated economic activities; cooperation among rural regions, exchange of experience and know-how concerning rural development.
Kazakhstan	Enhanced Partnership and Cooperation Agreement between the European Union and its Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Kazakhstan, of the other part	Article 229	Cooperation in the area of agriculture and rural development	Cooperation shall cover, among others, the following areas: (a) facilitating the mutual understanding of agricultural and rural development policies; (b) exchanging best practices in the planning, evaluation and implementation of agricultural and rural development policies; (c) sharing knowledge and best practices with regard to rural development policies to promote social and economic well-being for rural inhabitants; (d) promoting the modernisation and the sustainability of agricultural production; (e) improving the competitiveness of the agricultural sector and the efficiency and transparency of the markets; (f) exchanging experience in geographical indications for agricultural products and foodstuffs, in quality policies and their control mechanisms, in ensuring food safety and in the development of the production of organic agricultural products; (g) disseminating knowledge and promoting extension services to agricultural producers; (h) promoting cooperation in agro-industrial investments projects, in particular in the development of the livestock and crop sectors; (i) exchanging experience in policies related to sustainable development of agribusiness and the processing and distribution of agricultural products.
Kosovo	Stabilisation and association agreement between the European Union and the European Atomic Energy Community, of the one part, and Kosovo, of the other part	Article 102	Agriculture and the agro-industrial sector	Cooperation between the Parties shall be developed in all priority areas related to the EU acquis in the field of agriculture, as well as on quality schemes for agricultural products and foodstuffs, food safety, veterinary and phytosanitary domains. Cooperation shall notably aim at modernising and restructuring the agriculture and agro-industrial sector in Kosovo, particular to reach EU sanitary requirements, to improve water management and rural development as well as to develop the related aspects of the forestry sector in Kosovo and at supporting the gradual approximation of Kosovo legislation and practices to the EU

				acquis.
Lebanon	Euro-Mediterranean agreement establishing an association between the European Community and its Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Lebanon, of the other part	Article 51	Agriculture and fisheries	The aims of cooperation shall be: (a) to support policies aiming to diversify production; (b) to reduce food dependency; (c) to promote a form of agriculture which pays due regard to the environment; (d) to establish closer relations between enterprises, groupings and professional organisations of the two Parties; (e) to provide assistance and technical training; support for agronomic research, advisory services, agricultural education and technical training of staff in the agricultural sector; (f) to harmonise phytosanitary and veterinary standards; (g) to support integrated rural development, including improvement of basic services and development of ancillary economic activities, particularly in the regions affected by the eradication of illicit crops; (h) cooperation between rural areas, exchange of experience and know-how on rural development; (i) development of sea fishing and aquaculture; (j) development of packaging, storage and marketing techniques; and the improvement of distribution channels; (k) to develop agricultural water resources; (l) to develop the forestry sector, especially in the fields of reforestation, forest fire prevention, forest pasture and combating desertification; (m) to develop agricultural mechanisation and promotion of agricultural service cooperatives; (n) to strengthen the agricultural credit system.
Mexico	Economic Partnership, Political Coordination and Cooperation Agreement between the European Community and its Member States of the one part, and the United Mexican States, of the other part	Article 21	Cooperation in agriculture and the rural sector	1. The Parties undertake to promote development and cooperation in the agricultural, agroindustrial and rural sectors. 2. To this end they shall examine , inter alia, the following: (a) measures to harmonize health, plant-health and environmental standards and rules, with a view to facilitating trade, taking account of the legislation in force for both Parties and in conformity with the rules of the WTO, in addition to the terms of Article 5; (b) the potential for exchanging information and setting up projects and activities, with that aim in mind, notably in the fields of information, scientific and technical research and the development of human resources.
Moldova	Association agreement between the European Union and the European Atomic Energy Community and their	Article 68	Agriculture and rural development	Cooperation between the Parties in the field of agriculture and rural development shall cover, inter alia, the following areas: (a) facilitating the mutual understanding of agricultural and rural development policies; (b) enhancing the administrative capacities at central and local level in

	Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Moldova, of the other part			the planning, evaluation and implementation of policies in accordance with EU regulations and best practices; (c) promoting the modernisation and the sustainability of agricultural production; (d) sharing knowledge and best practices of rural development policies to promote economic well-being for rural communities; (e) improving the competitiveness of the agricultural sector and the efficiency and transparency of the markets; (f) promoting quality policies and their control mechanisms, in particular geographical indications and organic farming; (g) disseminating knowledge and promoting extension services to agricultural producers; and (h) enhancing the harmonisation of issues dealt within the framework of international organisations of which the Parties are members.
Montenegro	Stabilisation and association agreement between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Montenegro, of the other part	Article 97	Agriculture, and the agro-industrial sector	Cooperation between the Parties shall be developed in all priority areas related to the Community acquis in the field of agriculture, as well as veterinary and phytosanitary domains. Cooperation shall notably aim at modernising and restructuring the agriculture and agro-industrial sector, in particular to reach community sanitary requirements, to improve water management and rural development as well as to develop the forestry sector in Montenegro and at supporting the gradual approximation of Montenegrin legislation and practices to the Community rules and standards.
Morocco	Euro-Mediterranean agreement establishing an association between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Kingdom of Morocco, of the other part		Agriculture and fisheries	The aim of cooperation shall be to: (a) modernise and restructure agriculture and fisheries through methods including the modernisation of infrastructure and equipment, the development of packaging and storage techniques and the improvement of private distribution and marketing chains; (b) diversify output and external markets; (c) achieve cooperation in health, plant health and growing techniques.
North Macedonia	Stabilisation and association agreement between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the former Yugoslav Republic of	Article 100	Agriculture, and the agro-industrial sector	Cooperation in this field shall have as its aim the modernization and restructuring of agriculture and the agro-industrial sector, water management, rural development, the gradual harmonisation of veterinary and phytosanitary legislation with Community standards and the development of fishery and forestry sectors in the former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia.

	Macedonia, of the other part			
Palestinian Authority of the West Bank and the Gaza Strip	Council Decision of 2 June 1997 concerning the conclusion of the Euro-Mediterranean Interim Association Agreement on trade and cooperation between the European Community, of the one part, and the Palestine Liberation Organization (PLO) for the benefit of the Palestinian Authority of the West Bank and the Gaza Strip	-	-	No specific provision on agricultural trade/sector in connection to sustainability aspects
San Marino	Agreement on Cooperation and Customs Union between the European Economic Community and the Republic of San Marino	Article 6	-	In trade in agricultural products between the Community and San Marino, the Republic of San Marino undertakes to adopt Community veterinary, plant health and quality regulations where necessary for the proper functioning of the Agreement.
Serbia	Stabilisation and association agreement between the European Communities and their Member States of the one part, and the Republic of Serbia, of the other part	Article 97	Agriculture, and the agro-industrial sector	Cooperation between the Parties shall be developed in all priority areas related to the Community acquis in the field of agriculture, as well as veterinary and phytosanitary domains. Cooperation shall notably aim at modernising and restructuring the agriculture and agro-industrial sector, in particular to reach community sanitary requirements, to improve water management and rural development as well as to develop the forestry sector in Serbia and at supporting the gradual approximation of Serbian legislation and practices to the Community rules and standards.
Singapore	FREE TRADE AGREEMENT BETWEEN THE EUROPEAN UNION AND THE REPUBLIC OF SINGAPORE	-	-	No specific provision on agricultural trade/sector in connection to sustainability aspects
South Korea	Free Trade Agreement between the European Union and its Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of	-	-	No specific provision on agricultural trade/sector in connection to sustainability aspects

	Korea, of the other part			
Switzerland	Agreement between the European Economic Community and the Swiss Confederation	-	-	No specific provision on agricultural trade/sector in connection to sustainability aspects
Tunisia	Euro-Mediterranean agreement establishing an association between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Tunisia, of the other part	Article 54	Agriculture and fisheries	The aim of cooperation shall be to: (a) modernise and restructure agriculture and fisheries through methods including the modernisation of infrastructure and equipment, the development of packaging and storage techniques and the improvement of private distribution and marketing chains; (b) diversify output and external markets; (c) achieve cooperation in health, plant health and growing techniques.
Turkey	Decision No 1 /95 of the EC-Turkey association council on implementing the final phase of the Customs Union	-	-	No specific provision on agricultural trade/sector in connection to sustainability aspects
Ukraine	Association agreement between the European Union and the European Atomic Energy Community and their Member States, of the one part, and Ukraine, of the other part	Article 404	Agriculture and rural development	Cooperation between the Parties in the field of agriculture and rural development shall cover, inter alia, the following areas: (a) facilitating mutual understanding of agricultural and rural development policies; (b) enhancing administrative capacities at central and local levels for the planning, evaluation and implementation of policies; (c) promoting modern and sustainable agricultural production, respectful of the environment and of animal welfare, including extension of the use of organic production methods and the use of biotechnologies, inter alia through the implementation of best practices in those fields; (d) sharing knowledge and best practices of rural development policies to promote economic well-being for rural communities; (e) improving the competitiveness of the agricultural sector and the efficiency and transparency of the markets as well as conditions for investment; (f) disseminating knowledge through training and information events; (g) favouring innovation through research and promoting extension services to agricultural producers; (h) enhancing harmonisation of issues addressed within the framework of international organisations; (i) exchanging best practices on support mechanisms for agricultural

				policies and rural areas; (j) promoting the policy of quality of agricultural products in the areas of product standards, production requirements and quality schemes.
United Kingdom	Trade and Cooperation Agreement between the European Union and the European Atomic Energy Community, of the one part, and the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland, of the other part	Article 69	SANITARY AND PHYTOSANITARY MEASURES - Objectives	(e) enhance cooperation between the Parties in the fight against antimicrobial resistance, promotion of sustainable food systems, protection of animal welfare, and on electronic certification.
Viet Nam	Free Trade Agreement between the European Union and the Socialist Republic of Viet Nam	-	-	No specific provision on agricultural trade/sector in connection to sustainability aspects
Agreements being adopted or ratified				
Argentina, Brazil, Paraguay, Uruguay (Mercosur)	Trade part of the EU-Mercosur Association Agreement	CHAPTER DIALOGUES Article 3	Animal welfare	Recognizing that animals are sentient beings, the Parties will conduct a dialogue that will cover, inter alia: 1. Specific topics on animal welfare that may affect mutual trade; 2. Exchange of information, expertise and experiences in the field of animal welfare to improve their respective approaches on regulatory standards related to breeding, holding, handling, transportation and slaughter of animals to their mutual benefits. 3. Strengthen the research collaboration. 4. Collaboration in international fora with the aim to promote the further development of international standards on animal welfare by the World Organization for Animal Health (OIE) and best animal welfare practices and their implementation.
-//-	-//-	CHAPTER DIALOGUES Article 4	Agricultural biotechnology	This dialogue will cover, inter alia: 1. To exchange information on policies, legislation, guidelines, good practices, and projects of agricultural biotechnology products. 2. To discuss specific topics on biotechnology that may affect mutual trade, including cooperation on

				GMO testing. 3. To exchange information on topics related to asynchronous authorisations of genetically modified organisms in order to minimize possible impact on trade. 4. To exchange information on the economic and trade outlook of authorisations of genetically modified products; 5. To exchange information on cases of low level presence of GMOs non-authorised by the importing Party, but authorised by the exporting Party.
-//-	-//-	CHAPTER DIALOGUES Article 5	Combating antimicrobial resistance	This dialogue will cover, inter alia: 1. The collaboration to follow up existing and future guidelines, standards, recommendations and actions developed in relevant international organisations, initiatives and national plans aiming to promote the prudent and responsible use of antibiotics and relating to animal production and veterinary practices. 2. The collaboration in the implementation of the recommendations of OIE, WHO and Codex, in particular CAC-RCP61/2005. 3. The exchange of information on good farming practices. 4. The promotion of research, innovation and development. 5. The promotion of multidisciplinary approaches to combat antimicrobial resistance, including the One Health approach of WHO, OIE and Codex Alimentarius.
-//-	-//-	CHAPTER DIALOGUES Article 6	Scientific matters related to food safety, animal and plant health	1. The Parties should foster the cooperation between their respective official scientific bodies responsible for food safety, animal and plant health science. This cooperation will aim to deepen the scientific information available to the Parties in order to support their respective approaches on regulatory standards that may affect mutual trade.
Benin, Burkina Faso, Cabo Verde, Gambia, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Liberia, Mali, Mauritania, Niger, Nigeria, Senegal, Sierra Leone, Togo (West Africa)	Economic partnership agreement between the West African States, the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) and the West African Economic and Monetary Union (UEMOA), of the one part, and the European Union and its Member States, of the other part	-	-	No specific provision on agricultural trade/sector in connection to sustainability aspects

<p>Burundi, Kenya, Rwanda, Tanzania, Uganda (EAC)</p>	<p>Economic Partnership Agreement between the East African Community Partner States, of the one part, and the European Union and its Member States of the other part</p>	<p>Article 58</p>	<p>AGRICULTURE - Objectives</p>	<p>1. The Parties agree that the fundamental objective of this Part is sustainable agricultural development which includes but is not limited to food and livelihoods security, rural development and poverty reduction in the EAC Partner States.</p> <p>2. The objectives of this Part are to: (a) foster cooperation between the Parties with a view to creating wealth and improving the quality of life of those engaged in agricultural activities through increased production, productivity and market share. (b) improve food and nutrition security in the EAC Partner States by promoting value addition, increasing output, quality, safety, market integration, trade, availability and accessibility. (c) contribute to provision of gainful employment throughout the value chain of modernised agricultural sector. (d) develop modern and competitive agro-based industries. (e) promote sustainable use and management of natural and cultural resources by developing environmentally friendly and sustainable technologies that improve the agricultural productivity. (f) contribute to competitiveness by promoting value addition throughout the supply chains to access markets. (g) improve producers' revenue by developing the marketing of value added agricultural products in the marketplace (h) facilitate the adjustment of the agricultural sector and the rural economy, to cope with global economic changes (i) mobilize and increase the economic performance of small scale farmers through capacity building of farmers' organisations. (j) improve trade and market facilitation for agricultural commodities in order to increase foreign exchange earnings. (k) improve infrastructure within EAC Partner States for enhancing production, productivity, marketing and distribution of agricultural inputs and products, with particular attention to storage, grading, handling, packing and transport.</p>
<p>-//-</p>	<p>-//-</p>	<p>Article 59</p>	<p>AGRICULTURE - General Principles</p>	<p>1. The Parties recognise the importance of agriculture in EAC Partner States economies, as the main source of livelihood for the majority of the EAC Partner States' population, as the primary factor to ensure food and nutrition security, potential sector for high growth and added value and a source of export earnings.</p> <p>2. In view of the multi-functional role agriculture plays in the economy of the EAC Partner States, the Parties agree to use a comprehensive approach to agriculture as a basis for sustainable development.</p>

				<p>3. The Parties agree to cooperate in promoting the sustainable growth of the agriculture sector, taking into account its multiple facets and the diversity of the economic, social, environmental characteristics and development strategies of the EAC Partner States.</p> <p>4. The Parties recognize that deeper integration of the agricultural sector across the EAC Partner States will contribute to the expansion of inter-regional markets, and increase the scope for investment and private sector development.</p> <p>5. The Parties recognize the importance of supporting agricultural production, promotion of value addition, agricultural trade and market development initiatives through appropriate instruments and provision of appropriate regulatory framework to respond to changing market conditions. In this respect, the Parties resolve to work together to attract necessary investment into the EAC Partner States.</p> <p>6. The Parties agree that agricultural priorities considered in this Part shall be clearly linked to the regional overarching policy framework for food and nutrition security and poverty reduction to ensure consistency and guidance of the regional development agenda.</p>
-//-	-//-	Article 63	AGRICULTURE - Sustainable Agricultural Development	The Parties shall cooperate in achieving sustainable agricultural development with special focus on supporting vulnerable rural population in the EAC Partner States in light of the changing world production and trade patterns as well as consumer tastes and preference.
-//-	-//-	Article 64	AGRICULTURE - Food and Nutrition Security	<p>1. The Parties agree that the provisions of this Agreement shall enable the EAC Partner States implement effective measures to achieve food and nutrition security and sustainable agricultural development, and to develop commercial agricultural markets in the region to ensure food and nutrition security.</p> <p>2. The Parties shall ensure that actions taken under this Part aim at enhancing food and nutrition security, and avoiding adoption of measures that could endanger achievement of food and nutrition security at the household, national and regional levels.</p>
-//-	-//-	Article 65	AGRICULTURE - Value Chain	The Parties agree to have a regional strategy for enhancing supply capacities in agriculture, identifying high value agricultural sub-sectors for which the region has competitive advantage and capitalise on

			Management	investments that can facilitate the shift from comparative to competitive advantages.
-//-	-//-	Article 66	AGRICULTURE - Early Warning Systems	The Parties recognise the need to establish, improve and enhance food security information systems, including national early warning systems, as well as, vulnerability assessment and monitoring systems, and implement capacity building actions, in conjunction with and through existing international and regional mechanisms.
-//-	-//-	Article 67	AGRICULTURE - Technology	The Parties recognise the importance of modern and sustainable agricultural technologies and agree to develop and promote the use of modern agricultural technologies that include: (a) sustainable irrigation and fertigation technologies; (b) tissue culture and micro propagation; (c) improved seed; (d) artificial insemination; (e) integrated pest management; (f) product packaging; (g) post-harvest handling; (h) accredited laboratories; (i) biotechnologies; (j) risk assessment and management.
-//-	-//-	Article 71	AGRICULTURE - Net Food Importing Countries	<p>1. The Parties recognise the importance of addressing the concerns of net food importing EAC Partner States. The objective of this Article therefore is to assist countries that are net food importers to develop programmes to ensure food security.</p> <p>2. The Parties agree to: (a) address constraints for food production, storage and distribution in EAC region (b) source food aid from within the EAC Partner States and other African Regional Economic Communities (c) improve coordination of food aid</p> <p>3. The Parties agree to maintain an adequate level of food aid, taking into account the interests of food aid recipients and to ensure that the measures mentioned in paragraph 2 do not unintentionally impede the delivery of food aid provided to deal with emergency situations.</p> <p>4. The Parties shall ensure that food aid is provided in full conformity with the measures that aim at preventing commercial displacement, which include: (a) ensuring that all food aid transactions are need driven and in full grant form; (b) not tying them directly or indirectly to commercial exports of agricultural products or of other goods and services.</p>

-//-	-//-	Article 72	AGRICULTURE - Importance of certain sectors	<p>1. The Parties recognise that: (a) provision of adequate access to food, clean and safe drinking water, health facilities, educational opportunities, housing, community participation and social integration is important for livelihood security of rural populations; (b) agricultural infrastructure development including production, processing, marketing and distribution plays crucial role in EAC Partner States' social-economic rural development and regional integration; (c) technical support services such as agricultural research, extension and advisory services training are important in increasing agricultural productivity; (d) facilitating agricultural financing is an important measure for transforming the agricultural sector in the EAC Partner States. Financing is required for agricultural technology development, agricultural credit and insurance, infrastructure development and markets as well as farmers' training; and (e) sustainable rural development is important to improve standards of living of the rural population of EAC Partner States.</p> <p>2. The Parties agree to cooperate in livelihood security, agricultural infrastructure, technical support services, agricultural financing services and rural development as provided for in Title II of Part V.</p>
-//-	-//-	Article 74	AGRICULTURE - Geographical indications	<p>1. The Parties recognise the importance of geographical indications for sustainable agriculture and rural development.</p> <p>2. The Parties agree to cooperate in the identification, recognition and registration of products that could benefit from protection as geographical indications and any other action aimed at achieving protection for identified products.</p>
Haiti	Economic Partnership Agreement between the CARIFORUM States, of the one part, and the European Community and its Member States, of the other part	Article 37	Agriculture and fisheries - Objectives	<p>1. The Parties agree that the fundamental objective of this Agreement is the sustainable development and the eradication of poverty in CARIFORUM States, and the smooth and gradual integration of these economies into the global economy. In the agricultural and fisheries sectors, this Agreement should contribute to increasing the competitiveness of production, processing and trade in agricultural and fishery products in both traditional and non-traditional sectors, between the Parties, consistent with the sustainable management of natural resources.</p> <p>4. The Parties recognise that ensuring food security and enhancing</p>

				livelihoods of rural and fishing communities are critical elements of the eradication of poverty, and the pursuit of sustainable development. They consequently recognise the need to avoid major disruption of markets for agricultural, food and fish products in CARIFORUM States.
New Zealand	Free Trade Agreement between the European Union and New Zealand	Article 7.4	SUSTAINABLE FOOD SYSTEMS - Cooperation to improve the sustainability of food systems	4. The Parties shall cooperate on topics such as: (a) food production methods and practices which aim to improve sustainability, including organic farming and regenerative agriculture, amongst others; (b) the efficient use of natural resources and agricultural inputs, including reducing the use and risk of chemical pesticides and fertilisers, where appropriate; (c) the environmental and climate impacts of food production, including on agricultural greenhouse gas emissions, carbon sinks and biodiversity loss.

APPENDIX III: CASE STUDIES' RESPONSES TO QUESTIONNAIRES FOR THE RELEVANCE OF SDGS WITH POLICIES AS IMPLEMENTED LOCALLY

a. Organic farming certification

GOALS AND TARGETS (FROM THE 2030 AGENDA FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT)		6	1	4			
		ANALYSIS OF COCOA AND CHOCOLATE PURCHASING PRACTICES THAT COULD UNDERMINE LIVING INCOMES FOR COCOA FARMERS	Reducing poverty among smallholder farmers through enhanced trade regimes and value chains for coffee in Uganda and Tanzania	Priority intervention requirements to enhance the capacity of Sub Saharan African (SSA) countries to improve the volume and quality of agri-food exports			
				Cassava in Tanzania	Banana in Uganda	Goat Farming in Ethiopia	Cocoa in Ghana
GOAL 1. END POVERTY IN ALL ITS FORMS EVERYWHERE	1.1 By 2030, eradicate extreme poverty for all people everywhere, currently measured as people living on less than \$1.25 a day	3	1 0	1	3	1	3
	1.2 By 2030, reduce at least by half the proportion of men, women and children of all ages living in poverty in all its dimensions according to national definitions	3	1 0	1	3	1	3

GOAL 2. END HUNGER, ACHIEVE FOOD SECURITY AND IMPROVED NUTRITION AND PROMOTE SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURE

2.1 By 2030, end hunger and ensure access by all people, in particular the poor and people in vulnerable situations, including infants, to safe, nutritious and sufficient food all year round	3	0	0	1	3	1	0
2.3 By 2030, double the agricultural productivity and incomes of small-scale food producers, in particular women, indigenous peoples, family farmers, pastoralists and fishers, including through secure and equal access to land, other productive resources and inputs, knowledge, financial services, markets and opportunities for value addition and non-farm employment	3	1	0	3	3	3	2
2.4 By 2030, ensure sustainable food production systems and implement resilient agricultural practices that increase productivity and production, that help maintain ecosystems, that strengthen capacity for adaptation to climate change, extreme weather, drought, flooding and other disasters and that progressively improve land and soil quality	2	1	0	3	3	3	2
2.5 By 2020, maintain the genetic diversity of seeds, cultivated plants and farmed and domesticated animals and their related wild species, including through soundly managed and diversified seed and plant banks at the national, regional and international levels, and promote access to and fair and	-1	2	0	3	3	3	2

	equitable sharing of benefits arising from the utilization of genetic resources and associated traditional knowledge, as internationally agreed							
	2.b Correct and prevent trade restrictions and distortions in world agricultural markets, including through the parallel elimination of all forms of agricultural export subsidies and all export measures with equivalent effect, in accordance with the mandate of the Doha Development Round	1	1	0	3	3	1	0
	2.c Adopt measures to ensure the proper functioning of food commodity markets and their derivatives and facilitate timely access to market information, including on food reserves, in order to help limit extreme food price volatility	0	1	0	3	3	1	3
GOAL 6. ENSURE AVAILABILITY AND SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT OF WATER AND SANITATION FOR ALL	6.6 By 2020, protect and restore water-related ecosystems, including mountains, forests, wetlands, rivers, aquifers and lakes	0	0	0	3	3	3	3
GOAL 8. PROMOTE SUSTAINED, INCLUSIVE AND SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC GROWTH, FULL AND PRODUCTIVE EMPLOYMENT AND DECENT WORK FOR ALL	8.1 Sustain per capita economic growth in accordance with national circumstances and, in particular, at least 7 per cent gross domestic product growth per annum in the least developed countries	3	1	0	1	3	2	3
	8.2 Achieve higher levels of economic productivity through diversification, technological upgrading and innovation, including	1	1	1	3	3	2	3

	through a focus on high-value added and labour-intensive sectors							
	8.8 Protect labour rights and promote safe and secure working environments for all workers, including migrant workers, in particular women migrants, and those in precarious employment	1	1	0	3	3	2	3
GOAL 9. BUILD RESILIENT INFRASTRUCTURE, PROMOTE INCLUSIVE AND SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIALIZATION AND FOSTER INNOVATION	9.4 By 2030, upgrade infrastructure and retrofit industries to make them sustainable, with increased resource-use efficiency and greater adoption of clean and environmentally sound technologies and industrial processes, with all countries taking action in accordance with their respective capabilities	0	1	0	3	3	3	3
	9.b Support domestic technology development, research and innovation in developing countries, including by ensuring a conducive policy environment for, inter alia, industrial diversification and value addition to commodities	0	1	0	3	3	2	3
GOAL 10. REDUCE INEQUALITY WITHIN AND AMONG COUNTRIES	10.1 By 2030, progressively achieve and sustain income growth of the bottom 40 per cent of the population at a rate higher than the national average	3	1	0	3	3	2	3
	10.2 By 2030, empower and promote the social, economic and political inclusion of all, irrespective of age, sex, disability, race, ethnicity, origin, religion or economic or other status	2	1	0	3	3	2	3

GOAL 12. ENSURE SUSTAINABLE CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION PATTERNS	10.3 Ensure equal opportunity and reduce inequalities of outcome, including by eliminating discriminatory laws, policies and practices and promoting appropriate legislation, policies and action in this regard	1	1	0	3	3	2	3
	10.6 Ensure enhanced representation and voice for developing countries in decision-making in global international economic and financial institutions in order to deliver more effective, credible, accountable and legitimate institutions	3	1	0	3	3	3	3
	12.1 Implement the 10-Year Framework of Programmes on Sustainable Consumption and Production Patterns, all countries taking action, with developed countries taking the lead, taking into account the development and capabilities of developing countries	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
	12.2 By 2030, achieve the sustainable management and efficient use of natural resources	1	1	1	3	3	3	3
	12.4 By 2020, achieve the environmentally sound management of chemicals and all wastes throughout their life cycle, in accordance with agreed international frameworks, and significantly reduce their release to air, water and soil in order to minimize their adverse impacts on human health and the environment	1	1	2	1	1	1	1

	12.5 By 2030, substantially reduce waste generation through prevention, reduction, recycling and reuse	0	1	0	1	1	1	1
	12.a Support developing countries to strengthen their scientific and technological capacity to move towards more sustainable patterns of consumption and production	0		0	-3	-3	-3	-3
GOAL 13. TAKE URGENT ACTION TO COMBAT CLIMATE CHANGE AND ITS IMPACTS	13.2 Integrate climate change measures into national policies, strategies and planning			0	3	3	3	3
GOAL 14. CONSERVE AND SUSTAINABLY USE THE OCEANS, SEAS AND MARINE RESOURCES FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT	14.1 By 2025, prevent and significantly reduce marine pollution of all kinds, in particular from land-based activities, including marine debris and nutrient pollution	0	1	0	3	3	3	3
GOAL 15. PROTECT, RESTORE AND PROMOTE SUSTAINABLE USE OF TERRESTRIAL ECOSYSTEMS, SUSTAINABLY MANAGE FORESTS, COMBAT DESERTIFICATION, AND HALT AND REVERSE LAND DEGRADATION AND HALT BIODIVERSITY LOSS	15.1 By 2020, ensure the conservation, restoration and sustainable use of terrestrial and inland freshwater ecosystems and their services, in particular forests, wetlands, mountains and drylands, in line with obligations under international agreements	0	1	0	1	1	3	2
	15.3 By 2030, combat desertification, restore degraded land and soil, including land affected by desertification, drought and floods, and strive to achieve a land degradation-neutral world	0	1	0	1	1	3	2
	15.4 By 2030, ensure the conservation of mountain ecosystems, including their biodiversity, in order to enhance	0	1	0	1	1	3	2

	their capacity to provide benefits that are essential for sustainable development								
	15.5 Take urgent and significant action to reduce the degradation of natural habitats, halt the loss of biodiversity and, by 2020, protect and prevent the extinction of threatened species	1	1	0	1	1	3	2	

b. Food Safety Regulations

		1 Reducing poverty among smallholder farmers through enhanced trade regimes and value chains for coffee in Uganda and Tanzania		4 Priority intervention requirements to enhance the capacity of Sub Saharan African (SSA) countries to improve the volume and quality of agri-food exports			
				Cassava in Tanzania	Banana in Uganda	Goat Farming in Ethiopia	Cocoa in Ghana
Goal 1. End poverty in all its forms everywhere	1.1 By 2030, eradicate extreme poverty for all people everywhere, currently measured as people living on less than \$1.25 a day	-1	0	2	3	2	3
	1.2 By 2030, reduce at least by half the proportion of men, women and children of all ages living in poverty in all its dimensions according to national definitions	1	0	2	3	2	3
Goal 2. End hunger, achieve food security and improved	2.1 By 2030, end hunger and ensure access by all people, in particular the poor and people in vulnerable situations, including infants, to safe, nutritious and sufficient food all year round	1	0	3	3	2	3

nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture	2.3 By 2030, double the agricultural productivity and incomes of small-scale food producers, in particular women, indigenous peoples, family farmers, pastoralists and fishers, including through secure and equal access to land, other productive resources and inputs, knowledge, financial services, markets and opportunities for value addition and non-farm employment	1	0	3	3	3	3
	2.4 By 2030, ensure sustainable food production systems and implement resilient agricultural practices that increase productivity and production, that help maintain ecosystems, that strengthen capacity for adaptation to climate change, extreme weather, drought, flooding and other disasters and that progressively improve land and soil quality	2	0	3	3	3	3
	2.b Correct and prevent trade restrictions and distortions in world agricultural markets, including through the parallel elimination of all forms of agricultural export subsidies and all export measures with equivalent effect, in accordance with the mandate of the Doha Development Round	1	0	2	3	3	2
	2.c Adopt measures to ensure the proper functioning of food commodity markets and their derivatives and facilitate timely access to market information, including on food reserves, in order to help limit extreme food price volatility	1	0	2	3	3	3
Goal 3. Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages	3.9 By 2030, substantially reduce the number of deaths and illnesses from hazardous chemicals and air, water and soil pollution and contamination		2	3	2	1	2
Goal 8. Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable	8.1 Sustain per capita economic growth in accordance with national circumstances and, in particular, at least 7 per cent gross domestic product growth per annum in the least developed countries	2	0	2	3	2	3

economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all	8.2 Achieve higher levels of economic productivity through diversification, technological upgrading and innovation, including through a focus on high-value added and labour-intensive sectors	1	-1	2	3	2	3
	9.4 By 2030, upgrade infrastructure and retrofit industries to make them sustainable, with increased resource-use efficiency and greater adoption of clean and environmentally sound technologies and industrial processes, with all countries taking action in accordance with their respective capabilities	-1	0	3	3	2	3
Goal 9. Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation	9.b Support domestic technology development, research and innovation in developing countries, including by ensuring a conducive policy environment for, inter alia, industrial diversification and value addition to commodities	1	0	3	3	2	3
	10.1 By 2030, progressively achieve and sustain income growth of the bottom 40 percent of the population at a rate higher than the national average	1	0	2	3	2	3
Goal 10. Reduce inequality within and among countries	10.2 By 2030, empower and promote the social, economic and political inclusion of all, irrespective of age, sex, disability, race, ethnicity, origin, religion or economic or other status	1	0	2	3	2	3
	10.3 Ensure equal opportunity and reduce inequalities of outcome, including by eliminating discriminatory laws, policies and practices and promoting appropriate legislation, policies and action in this regard	1	0	2	3	2	3
	10.4 Adopt policies, especially fiscal, wage and social protection policies, and progressively achieve greater equality	1	0	2	2	2	3
	10.6 Ensure enhanced representation and voice for developing countries in decision-making in global international economic and financial institutions in order to deliver more effective, credible, accountable and legitimate institutions	1	0	1	2	2	3
Goal 12. Ensure	12.1 Implement the 10-Year Framework of Programmes	1	0	1	1	2	2

sustainable consumption and production patterns	on Sustainable Consumption and Production Patterns, all countries taking action, with developed countries taking the lead, taking into account the development and capabilities of developing countries						
	12.2 By 2030, achieve the sustainable management and efficient use of natural resources	1	1	3	3	2	3
	12.4 By 2020, achieve the environmentally sound management of chemicals and all wastes throughout their life cycle, in accordance with agreed international frameworks, and significantly reduce their release to air, water and soil in order to minimize their adverse impacts on human health and the environment	1	3	3	3	2	3
	12.a Support developing countries to strengthen their scientific and technological capacity to move towards more sustainable patterns of consumption and production	1	0	3	3	2	3

APPENDIX IV: CASE STUDIES' RECOMMENDATIONS PRESENTED IN MATS POLICY BRIEFS AND REPORTS

Case Study	Proposed Policy Recommendations
CS1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Revive and empower farmer cooperatives. Public and private partnership should be established by the local government. • Implement tailored risk management programs for smallholder farmers. Introduce insurance schemes to offset production, marketing, and price volatility risks. Capacity building initiatives should accompany these programs. • Policy reforms favouring cooperatives' sustainability. • Provide adequate financial support to the Tanzania Coffee Board (TCB) to enhance its regulatory capacity and enforcement mechanisms. Invest in capacity building, foster partnerships, advocate for policy reforms, explore innovative financing mechanisms, and implement robust monitoring and evaluation systems. • Recognize family labour within fair trade certification, ensure transparent pricing that accounts for labour inputs, educate farmers on fair trade principles and negotiation skills, advocate for supportive policies to protect labour rights, foster community dialogue to integrate fair labour practices, and incorporate fair treatment of family labour into certification requirements. • Revise and operationalize the coffee related policies to address the constraints affecting effective and profitable participation of smallholder farmers. • Synergy and integration among the various levels of the value chain actors. • Create smallholder farmer' awareness about available agribusiness based digital services and improve physical infrastructure development for digital access and lower costs associated with access to the internet and digital devices. • Reequip agricultural extension service providers with modern working tools that can assist them to operate in a digitized agricultural world. • Address the disconnection between producing and consuming countries through coherent, reformed, and supportive international policy agenda, sustainability standards and operating environment.
CS3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When comparing carbon tax imposed on industries versus establishing carbon tax on dairy trade, at least in terms of emissions, it may be more efficient to impose regulations directly to the industry. • Instead of carbon taxing, it may be more efficient to reformulate the Common Agricultural Policy such that, instead of granting the hectare and animal-based support, the support would be based on the environmental and climate protection measures in peat lands, carbon farming in mineral lands, animal welfare measures, using low- emission feeds and by applying precision farming. • Environmental performance based subsidies may be an option in the future instead of area and animal head based subsidies.
CS14	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eradicate illegal deforestation. • Understand the interest and direction of China's policies in future soy and meat imports. • Support strategies focused on establishing a national public system for socio-environmental traceability. • Include other wooded lands and natural grasslands in the future revision of the EU Regulation on deforestation-free products.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adopt gradual and integrated trade-related measures that align with the dimensions of economic instruments and land regularization.
CS15 Transnational level	<p><u>Review Free Trade Agreements</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Revise free trade agreements to ensure a more balanced and fair relationship. • Address power imbalances by involving civil society in the negotiation process and establishing mechanisms for monitoring sustainability outcomes. <p><u>Forge a North African Trade Coalition</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthen the negotiating capacity of North African countries by forming a unified platform for agricultural trade negotiations with the EU. <p><u>Invest in Agroecology to Support a Just Agricultural Transition</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide targeted financial and public policy support to small-scale food producers to enable the spread of agroecological practices. • Partner with civil society and research institutions. • End support for the expansion of unsustainable monocultures. <p><u>Balance Agricultural Subsidies</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Address unequal support challenges by advocating for a fairer distribution of agricultural subsidies and assistance between European and North African countries. • Assert the same right to a just transition for agriculture in North Africa as in Europe. • Urge Europe to cease its support for austerity policies in North Africa. <p><u>Foster Agricultural Research Partnerships</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bolster the capacity of North African nations in agricultural research, innovation, and technology transfer. <p><u>Empower Small Farmers', Agricultural Workers' and Trade Justice Organizations</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Defend the rights of farmers and agricultural workers to organize and ensure their voices are influential in regional policy discussions. • Protect small-scale food producers' rights to land, water, seeds and plant genetic resources.
CS15 National level	<p><u>Develop a Food Sovereignty Strategy</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Partner with regional organizations to develop a food sovereignty strategy, promoting local production and self-sufficiency. <p><u>Support Territorial Markets</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adopt the 2016 Policy Recommendations of the UN Committee on World Food Security to enact public policies to support local, national, and regional food systems. <p><u>Adopt Sustainable Water Management</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote the adoption of water preservation techniques, and sustainable irrigation systems as well as the use of less water intensive, locally-adapted varieties. • Increase transparency around water use rights and allocation and strengthen participatory water governance systems. • Use tools such as the 'water footprint' to measure the trade in embedded water resources. <p><u>Enact Appropriate Food Standards</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop own standards and norms, drawing on indigenous knowledge, local plant varieties and animal breeds, and local consumer preferences. <p><u>Expand Public Agricultural Extension Services</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agricultural extension services provide farmers with the training and resources needed for sustainable agricultural practices. <p><u>Enact and Enforce Gender-Inclusive Policies</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recognize and address the role of women in the agricultural sector by

	<p>instituting gender-sensitive policies and promoting women's empowerment.</p> <p><u>Improve Farmworker Rights and Remunerations</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Ensure adequate working conditions and remuneration for farmworkers. <p><u>Fortify the Cooperative Sector</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Strengthen the cooperative sector and enhance the representativeness within cooperative membership.
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